

KPIs and assessments on nuclear H2 economic feasibility compared with other types of H2

Stéphanie Crevon (CEA), Cécile Diamantis (CEA),
Martin Silhan (CVR), Javier Calle Martí (Tecnatom),
Cecilia Herrero Moriana (Tecnatom)

Deliverable 3.3, Rev A

01.08.2024

Revisions

IND REV	RELEASE DATE	PARAGRAPH	SCOPE OF THE REVISION
A	See Cover Page	All	First Issue

ECCN: N

AL: N

Table of contents

Preface.....	10
Summary.....	11
1 Introduction	12
2 Current situation of hydrogen in Europe	13
2.1 Worldwide hydrogen consumption and production.....	13
2.2 European current consumption	14
2.3 European current production.....	16
2.4 European trade of hydrogen	19
3 Potential market of hydrogen in Europe.....	20
3.1 Potential evolution of the hydrogen markets	20
4 Required infrastructures for a competitive, realistic hydrogen market.	42
4.1 Facing the challenge of H ₂ European production.....	42
4.2 Challenges for the electricity grid.....	45
4.3 Challenges for hydrogen transport.....	49
4.4 Challenges for the gas infrastructure.....	51
5 Comparison between nuclear H₂ with other technologies	57
5.1 Different H ₂ colors.....	57
5.2 Choose of relevant KPIs	58
5.3 Technical comparison	59
5.4 Economical comparison.....	67
5.5 Environmental aspects	77
6 Conclusion.....	79
7 Bibliography	80
8 Annexes	85
8.1 Annex 1 – European consumption and production, full tables.....	85
8.2 Annex 2 – Methanation and separation	92
8.3 Annex 3 – Hydrogen Backbone – details on corridors	94
8.4 Annex 4 – Emerging hydrogen applications: Transport	100
8.5 Annex 5 – Co-electrolysis of carbon dioxide and water.	102

 AL: N
 ECCN: N

Index of Tables

Table 1: Emissions impact of transport in 2017	35
Table 2: Summary of the techno-economic and environmental KPIs chosen for the comparison ..	58
Table 3: Comparison of Hydrogen specification in National Standards for China [32]	58
Table 4: Summary of advantages and drawbacks of SMR, POX and ATR [42].....	59
Table 5: Summary of the main technical characteristics of AEL, PEM and SOEC technologies [48] [49]	65
Table 6: Summary of the main technical characteristics of AEL, PEM, SOEC technologies and SMR, SMR+CCUS POX, ATR, Coal gasification processes [50]	66
Table 7: Average gas prices from 2019 to 2023 (Aleasoft database [51]), and ETS tariff for CO₂	69
Table 8: Projected costs of generating electricity 2020 - IEA and NEA, for NPP at 85% capacity factor and WACC of 7%, new build and with LTO of 20 years.....	74
Table 9: Capacity factor and corresponding electrolyzer size according to electricity sourcing [1] [16]	76
Table 10: European hydrogen consumption by country in 2022 (t/yr) [2]	85
Table 11: European hydrogen consumption by end-use in 2022 (t/yr) [3]	86
Table 12: European hydrogen consumption by country and end-use in 2022 (t/yr) [3]	87
Table 13: European clean hydrogen consumption by country and end-use in 2022 (t/year) [2].....	88
Table 14: European hydrogen production capacity by country in 2022 (t/yr) [2].....	89
Table 15: European hydrogen production capacity by process type and end-use in 2022 (t/yr) [2]	90
Table 16: European hydrogen production capacity by country and process type in 2022 (t/year) [2]	91

AL: N
ECCN: N

Table of figures

	Figure 1: Hydrogen use by region (2022) [1]	13
	Figure 2: Hydrogen use by sector 2020 - 2030 [1]	13
	Figure 3: Global hydrogen production (IEA).....	14
	Figure 4: Hydrogen consumption by country in 2022	14
	Figure 5: Share of European hydrogen consumption in 2022 by end-use.....	15
	Figure 6: European clean hydrogen consumption in 2022 by end use [2].....	16
	Figure 7: European hydrogen production capacity and annual output in 2022 [2]	17
	Figure 8: European production capacity and annual output by country in 2022.....	18
	Figure 9: Map of hydrogen production sites in Europe in 2022 [3]	18
	Figure 10: Europe's 5 top hydrogen trade routes in 2022 [2].....	19
	Figure 11: Traditional and emerging uses of hydrogen [CEA]	20
	Figure 12: Use of hydrogen in Refineries.	21
	Figure 13: Hydrogen consumption in refineries, worldwide.	21
	Figure 14: Hydrogen consumption for refining in Europe	22
	Figure 15: Hydrogen for ammonia production in Europe (2022) [2].....	23
	Figure 16: Expected ammonia demand up to 2050 for the 1.5°C scenario [5].....	24
	Figure 17: Potential roles of ammonia in the hydrogen economy [5]	25
	Figure 18: Ammonia demand estimates for use as maritime fuel by 2050 from various sources [5]	26
	
	Figure 19: Overview of the steelmaking process [9]	27
	Figure 20: DRI route (source: Grinhy Project)	28
	Figure 21: Hydrogen consumption for direct reduction iron.....	29
	Figure 22: map of EU steel production sites [14]	30
	Figure 23: Feedstock and applications of methanol.	31
	Figure 24: Hydrogen consumption for methanol production.....	32
	Figure 25: Methanol production: traditional route (left), with CO₂ Capture unit (right)	33
	Figure 26: H₂ Consumption for other chemicals (2022)	33
	Figure 27: hydrogen production capacity other chemicals without by-products capacities	34
	Figure 28: hydrogen use for emerging applications.	35
	Figure 29: Overview of selected renewables energy carriers.....	36
	Figure 30: SAF approved production pathways [19].....	38
	Figure 31: ReFuelEu modelled SAF supply per production pathway in the EU27 and associated H₂	38
	needs	
	Figure 32: Natural gas final energy consumption for 2017 in the EU industry sector by application	39
	temperature.....	
	Figure 33: Working temperatures for selected renewables heat technologies and temperature	39
	requirement of selected industries.....	
	Figure 34: European green hydrogen demand estimates (2035).....	40
	Figure 35: Electrolyser average unit size vs number of sites in Europe	41
	Figure 36: Legislative policies adopted or revised in the Fit for 55 package and related to hydrogen	43
	[2].....	

N
ECCN:
N
AL:

AL: N
ECCN: N

Figure 37: View of the 12 legislations related to hydrogen identified and highlight on the ones that are detailed in the next sections 43

Figure 38: Carbon intensity of hydrogen produced from electrical grid, compared to selected benchmarks [3]..... 46

Figure 39: Map of European salt deposits and salt structures as a result of suitability assessment for underground hydrogen storage..... 48

Figure 40: Total salt cavern storage potential in European countries [24]..... 48

Figure 41: Gas/electricity hybrid energy system. 51

Figure 42: Methane and hydrogen gas grid configurations [CEA] 52

Figure 43: Methane and hydrogen conversion services [28]..... 52

Figure 44: EHB network map 2030. 54

Figure 45: EHB network map 2040. 55

Figure 46: Hydrogen color classification. 57

Figure 47: SMR process. 60

Figure 48: POX process..... 61

Figure 49: ATR process. 61

Figure 50: Coal gasification [31]..... 62

Figure 51: Carbon capture opportunities for SMR and ATR processes. 63

Figure 52: Overview of the different options for carbon capture [47]..... 64

Figure 53: Carbon capture and usage or storage..... 64

Figure 54: average levelized hydrogen production costs by technology in Europe in 2022 [34] 67

Figure 55: Picture of LCOH found in the literature for three years (2022, 2023 and 2030), for different countries and for different colors of hydrogen [CEA] 68

Figure 56: LCOH breakdown for SMR technologies. 69

Figure 57: LCOH breakdown for SMR + CCUS from 2019 to 2023 70

Figure 58: Electrolyzer CAPEX from 2020 to 2022 and forecast..... 71

Figure 59: LCOH Breakdown in Germany for electrolytic hydrogen supplied by the grid. 72

Figure 60 - LCOH breakdown according to PV load factor. 73

Figure 61: LCOH breakdown according to wind load factor..... 74

Figure 62: LCOH breakdown for different LCOE of nuclear electricity 75

Figure 63: LCOH comparison for different hydrogen production technologies, 2023..... 76

Figure 64: Carbon intensity of hydrogen produced from grid electricity [3] 77

Figure 65: Comparison of the emissions intensity of different hydrogen production [1] 78

Figure 66: Block scheme of the Sabatier process with recycled reactor 92

Figure 67: North Africa and Southern Europe corridor..... 94

Figure 68: North Africa and Southern Europe corridor..... 95

Figure 69: North Sea corridor. 96

Figure 70: Nordic and Baltic regions corridor..... 97

Figure 71: East and Southeastern Europe corridor..... 98

Figure 72 Hydrogen transmission network in Germany 99

Figure 73: Fuel cell operation diagram 100

Figure 74: Arrangement of components in a FCEV 101

Figure 75: Electrochemical reduction of CO₂ pathways. 102

Figure 76: Co-electrolysis of CO₂ and H₂O 103
Figure 77: Carbon dioxide electrolysis Pourboix diagram. 103
Figure 78: AEM co-electrolysis configuration..... 104
Figure 79: RB-BPM co-electrolysis configuration. 104
Figure 80: FB-BPM co-electrolysis configuration..... 104
Figure 81: Electrocatalytic reduction of carbon dioxide and water in a SOEC..... 105

ECCN: N

AL: N

Abbreviations and acronyms

Acronym	Description
AEF	Electric Arc Furnace
AEL	Anion Exchange Layer
AEM	Anion Exchange Membrane
AEUG	Advisory & End-Users Group
AFIR	Alternative Fuel Infrastructure Regulation
ASU	Air Separation Unit
ATR	Autothermal Reforming
BEV	Battery Electric Vehicles
BF-BOF	Blast Furnace
BOF	Basic Oxygen Furnace
BPM	Bipolar Membrane
CAPEX	CAPital EXpenditure
CCS	Carbon Capture and Storage
CCU	Carbon Capture and Utilization
CCUS	Carbon Capture Utilization and Storage
CEL	Cation Exchange Layer
CGH ₂	Compressed Hydrogen
CO ₂ RR	Electrochemical Reduction of CO ₂
CRL	Commercial Readiness Level
DAC	Direct Air Capture
DoA	Description of Action
DRI	Direct Reduction of Iron
EFTA	European Free Trade Association
EHB	European Hydrogen Backbone
EIGA	European Industrial Gases Association
ENTSOG	European Network of Transmission System Operators for Gas
ExCom	Executive Committee
FB-BPM	Forward Bias Bipolar Membrane
FCEV	Fuel Cell Electric Vehicles
GB	Governing Board
GHG	Greenhouse Gas
HEFA	Hydroprocessed Esters and Fatty Acids
HER	Hydrogen Evolution Reaction
HTSE	High Temperature Steam Electrolysis
HVO	Hydrotreated Vegetable Oil
ICE	Internal Combustion Engine
IEA	International Energy Agency
IRENA	International Renewable Energy Agency
JRC	Joint Research Centre
LCOE	Levelized Cost of Electricity
LCOH	Levelized Cost of Hydrogen
LH ₂	Liquified Hydrogen
LHV	Low Heating Value
LOHC	Liquid Organic Hydrogen Carriers
LTE	Low Temperature Electrolysis
LTO	Long Term Operation

AL: N
ECCN: N

MEA	Membrane Electrode Assembly
MEGC	Multiple Element Gas Container
MUG	Makeup Gas
OPEX	Operational EXpenditure
PEM	Proton Exchange Membrane
PPA	Power Purchase Agreement
POX	Partial Oxidation
PQP	Project Quality Plan
PSA	Pressure Swing Adsorption
PYR	Pyrolysis
PTG/P2G	Power to Gas
PTL/P2L	Power to Liquid
PV	PhotoVoltaic
RB-BPM	Reverse Bias Bipolar Membrane
RED	Renewable Energy Directive
RFNBO	Renewable Fuels of Non-Biological Origin
RHE	Reversible Hydrogen Electrode
SMR	Steam Methane Reforming
SOEC	Solid Oxide Electrolysis Cells
TDI	Toluene Diisocyanate
TRL	Technology Readiness Level
TSA	Temperature Swing Adsorption
TSO	Transmission System Operator
VALCOE	Value-Added Levelized Cost of Electricity
WGSR	Water Gas Shift Reaction
WP	Work Package
WPL	Work Package Leader

AL: N
ECCN: N

Preface

The content of this deliverable is the result of the combination of work provided by different project partners, each being responsible for the veracity and quality of their work. The distribution of work was the was the following:

CEA: Current situation of hydrogen in Europe, potential market of hydrogen in Europe, required infrastructures for a competitive, realistic hydrogen market and comparison between nuclear hydrogen with other technologies.

CVR: Literature review on LCOH of different technologies.

Tecnatom: Literature review on current situation of hydrogen in Europe, potential market of hydrogen in Europe, required infrastructures for a competitive, realistic hydrogen market and other ways to produce hydrogen. Annexes 2, 3, 4, 5. Review of the deliverable.

ECCN: N

AL: N

Summary

This document describes the European hydrogen market, the required infrastructures to support the development of hydrogen production and it compares the LCOH of different hydrogen production technologies.

In the first section of the document (Section 2), the current European hydrogen market is described with a focus on consumption, production and trade of hydrogen.

In the second section (Section 3), the potential market of hydrogen in Europe is estimated for each hydrogen application: refining, ammonia, steel, methanol, other chemical uses and other industrial uses, transport, e-fuels and industrial heat. In the last sub-section, average unitary electrolyzer sizes for each application are gathered.

In the third section (Section 4), challenges for a large development of hydrogen production in Europe are detailed: regulatory challenges, electricity grid supply, transportation of hydrogen and required infrastructure.

In the fourth section (Section 5), different production routes of hydrogen are compared from a technical, an economical and an environmental point of view. After a literature review comparing the LCOH for each production route and highlighting that assumptions highly differs from one study to another, a comparison with harmonized assumptions is proposed.

N
ECCN:

N
AL:

1 Introduction

The purpose of the **Deliverable 3.3** is to estimate the potential European H₂ market and required infrastructures and to estimate and compare Levelized Cost Of Hydrogen (LCOH) and other key indicators with different production technologies.

A first part of the report describes the current consumption, production and trade of hydrogen in Europe. The second part estimates the potential market in the next years for each identified uses of hydrogen. The third part presents the regulatory framework and the required infrastructure (electricity supply and hydrogen transport) to support a hydrogen production development. Finally, the last part compares different hydrogen production technologies in terms of LCOH and carbon emissions.

The Deliverable 3.3, KPIs and assessments on nuclear H₂ economic feasibility compared with other types of H₂, has been developed during Task 3.3 of WP3 that corresponds to Economic Roadmap.

ECCN: N

AL: N

2 Current situation of hydrogen in Europe

2.1 Worldwide hydrogen consumption and production

The worldwide hydrogen consumption was about 95 Mt in 2022. It has increased by 3% compared with 2021, continuing the growing trend. China and North America are the largest consumers of hydrogen accounting respectively 29% and 17% of global hydrogen use. Europe consumed 8% of the global hydrogen use in 2022. “Global Hydrogen Review 2023”IEA. [1]

Hydrogen use by region, 2022

Figure 1: Hydrogen use by region (2022) [1]

Figure 2 presents the hydrogen use by sector [1]. The two main applications nowadays are refining and industry (H₂ as a feedstock to produce ammonia, methanol and other chemicals). By 2030, new applications will emerge: transport, synfuels or power (Figure 2).

Figure 2: Hydrogen use by sector 2020 - 2030 [1]

Hydrogen production is dominated by unabated use of fossil fuels (Figure 3). Hydrogen is traditionally produced with natural gas (62% in 2022), coal (21%) or oil (0,5%). It can also be a by-product (16% in 2022) from other industries like chlore-alkali electrolysis or refineries. Coal gasification is mainly located in China while other countries mainly use natural gas. Low-carbon production ways are emerging with carbon capture and use (0,6%) and electrolysis (0,1%).

AL: N
ECCN: N
N

IEA. CC BY 4.0.

Note: CCUS= carbon capture, utilisation and storage.

Figure 3: Global hydrogen production (IEA)

2.2 European current consumption

In 2022, the total demand for hydrogen in the 27 EU Member States, European Free Trade Association (EFTA) (Iceland, Liechtenstein, Norway and Switzerland) and the UK (referred to as Europe in the rest of the section) was 8,2 Mt. Figure 4 presents the European hydrogen consumption by country in 2022, extracted from European Hydrogen Observatory [2]. Complete tables with Member States breakdown are in Annex 1, section 8.1.

Germany (21,2%), the Netherlands (12,0%), Poland (9,6%) and Spain (7,5%) was responsible for more than half of total hydrogen consumption in Europe.

Figure 4: Hydrogen consumption by country in 2022

Figure 5 shows the breakdown of European hydrogen consumption by end use, extracted from European Hydrogen Observatory [2]. The refining (57 %) and ammonia (24 %) sectors together account

for 81 % of the total consumption of hydrogen in Europe. Hydrogen is also used in various industries like methanol production (3 %) or other chemicals (9 %). Hydrogen as a fuel for industrial heat (3 %) is the biggest emerging application. Other emerging applications, using clean hydrogen, represent less than 0,05% each: mobility (0,043%), blending in natural gas pipelines (0,023%), hydrogen for direct reduced iron in the steel industry (0,019%), e-fuels (0,013%), residential heat (0,003%) and power generation (0,001%).

Figure 5: Share of European hydrogen consumption in 2022 by end-use

The Figure 6 hereunder presents the European clean hydrogen consumption by end-use [2]. Clean hydrogen represents only 0,24% of the total 2022 consumption (19 kt). Emerging applications are the driver of clean hydrogen demand with 41% of the total of clean hydrogen consumption (8,09 kt). Traditional applications such as Ammonia or refining represents respectively 12% and 9% of the clean hydrogen consumption.

AL: N
ECCN: N

Figure 6: European clean hydrogen consumption in 2022 by end use [2]

N
ECCN:
N
AL:

2.3 European current production

According to the European Hydrogen Observatory [2], the European hydrogen production capacity is about 11,3 Mt per year (Figure 7), for 476 production plants. Traditional hydrogen production by methane reforming represents 91% of production capacity (10 311 kt) and hydrogen produced as a by-product 8,6% (974 kt). Clean hydrogen capacity amounts for only 0,42% of hydrogen production capacity in Europe (29 kt from water electrolysis and 19 kt from reforming with carbon capture). In 2022, the utilization rate of these capacities was about 73% with a total annual output of 8,23 kt/year. Complete tables with Member States breakdown and process use breakdown are in Annex 1, section 8.1.

Figure 7: European hydrogen production capacity and annual output in 2022 [2]

By-product hydrogen comes from ethylene production, chlor-alkali process, styrene production and sodium chlorate production. Only three hydrogen production plants by reforming are equipped with carbon capture technologies (Grupo Sappio – Matova IT, Air Liquide – Port Jerome FR, Shell – Rotterdam NL). At the end of 2022, 97 water electrolysis hydrogen production projects (67 with a minimum capacity of 0,5 MW) were in operation in Europe, totaling 174,28 MW of production capacity and producing about 30.000 tons of hydrogen annually, representing 0,3 % of the overall total hydrogen production capacity.

The following figure presents the European production capacity and the annual output by country. Nine countries amount to 80% of annual production: Germany (21%), the Netherlands (12%), Poland (10%), Spain (7%), Italy (7%), the United Kingdom (7%), France (7%), Belgium (5%) and Greece (4%).

Figure 8: European production capacity and annual output by country in 2022

Figure 9, extracted from the report “Clean Hydrogen Monitor” [3], visualizes production sites and their relative production capacities. Most of the large-scale production is centralized in industrial areas and ports near refineries, ammonia producers, and chemical plants. The average size of conventional plants in 2022 was 42,7 kt/year for reforming process, between 5 and 10 kt/year for by-product hydrogen.

AL: N
ECCN: N

Figure 9: Map of hydrogen production sites in Europe in 2022 [3]

2.4 European trade of hydrogen

Production capacities can be divided in two types: captive hydrogen (hydrogen is consumed by an on-site facility) and merchant hydrogen (external distribution and sale). In Europe, 87% of the total production capacity is constituted by captive hydrogen and 13% by merchant hydrogen.

Merchant hydrogen is either produced by facilities operated by industrial gas producers dedicated to a single major consumer and with any surplus capacity for retail hydrogen market or produced by small and medium scale hydrogen production sites dedicated to retail market.

Less than 0,5% (34 kt) of produced hydrogen is traded between European Member States. The following figure presents the Europe's top 5 hydrogen trade routes in 2022. Hydrogen export from Belgium to the Netherlands is the biggest route with 75% of all the hydrogen traded in Europe. Other routes are Belgium-Luxembourg, Netherlands–Belgium, Netherlands–Germany and Sweden–Denmark.

Figure 10: Europe's 5 top hydrogen trade routes in 2022 [2]

AL: N
ECCN: N

3 Potential market of hydrogen in Europe

3.1 Potential evolution of the hydrogen markets

The following figure presents traditional and emerging uses of hydrogen. Hydrogen is traditionally used as feedstock in refineries and for ammonia and methanol production. For these three applications, the hydrogen production is highly integrated in the process and the replacement of the hydrogen production is not so easy. In other traditional industrial uses such as glass production (H₂ as reductant), food industry, semi-conductor (H₂ as reductant) and the chemical industry (H₂ as feedstock), the needs for hydrogen are lower and there is no integration between hydrogen production and the industrial process. Consequently, the switch for green hydrogen would be easier. Emerging uses of hydrogen are the steel manufacturing, mobility, blending in natural gas pipelines, e-fuels, industrial heat, residential heat and power generation.

Figure 11: Traditional and emerging uses of hydrogen [CEA]

3.1.1 Refining

3.1.1.1 H₂ use for refining: description and current use.

Refining is the first use of hydrogen in the world with 41 Mt in 2022 [1]. Today, 37% of the hydrogen consumed in refineries is a by-product of the refineries (naphta-cracking by example), 43% is produced on site and 20% is produced externally. In Figure 12, extracted from Linde industrial Gases website [4], is represented the production and use of hydrogen in refineries.

Figure 12: Use of hydrogen in Refineries.

As mentioned by IEA, “Merchant hydrogen sourced by refineries is typically produced in plants very close to the refinery, and sometimes even in the same location, but in plants operated by another company, given that hydrogen is not a global commodity today”. Less than 1% of hydrogen use in refineries was produced using low-emissions technologies. In 2030, the IEA plans a reduction for oil products resulting in a decrease for hydrogen use in refineries. The share of low-emissions hydrogen would be 15% in 2030.

Figure 13: Hydrogen consumption in refineries, worldwide.

European use of hydrogen for refining represents 11,3% (4,6 Mt) of the worldwide use of hydrogen for refining. Germany is by far the first European consumer of hydrogen for refining with 872 kt of hydrogen consumed in 2022. Height countries (Germany, Italy, Spain, Netherlands, Poland, France, United Kingdom and Greece) amount for 77% of European hydrogen consumption for refining. There are 78 plants using hydrogen for refining in Europe. Clean hydrogen represents only 0,04% of

hydrogen consumption for refining and clean hydrogen production takes place in only two countries: Germany with 1 742 t and Finland with 79 t.

Figure 14: Hydrogen consumption for refining in Europe

N
ECCN: N

3.1.1.2 H₂ use for refining: potential market.

Only refineries with hydrocrackers have to add on-site hydrogen production. The others are self-sufficient in hydrogen (hydrogen co-production). In Europe, there are 26 out of 74 refineries with hydrocrackers. The corresponding hydrogen consumption is about 1470 kt of hydrogen per year. This hydrogen is currently produced by Steam Methane Reforming (SMR). One way of decarbonizing refineries could be to replace this grey hydrogen by electrolytic hydrogen. The typical need of hydrogen per site is about 5,5 kt/h, that is 275 MW of electrolyzer capacity.

Eleven European projects from 10 to 300 MW of electrolyzer for refineries are under progress totaling 1,65 GW of electrolyzer capacity in 2030 (i.e. 264 kt H₂/year).

In the longer term, with the electrification of transportation and CO₂ neutrality targets, European demand for oil products will decrease and some refineries will close, other will be shifted in bio-refineries. Operators are not willing to invest in green hydrogen production in this context.

E-fuels and bio-refineries are detailed in 3.1.7.2.

3.1.2 Ammonia

3.1.2.1 H₂ use for ammonia production: description and current use.

In 2022, about 32 Mt of hydrogen was used for ammonia production worldwide according to IEA [1]. European ammonia production represents only 6,3% of the worldwide production with 2 Mt of ammonia. Poland and Germany are the two first countries for the use of hydrogen for ammonia production with respectively 18,7% and 17,8% of the total European use. Seven countries amount for

N
AL:

70% of the hydrogen used for ammonia production: Poland, Germany, the Netherlands, France, Belgium, the United Kingdom and Lithuania. There are 36 plants producing ammonia in Europe.

Figure 15: Hydrogen for ammonia production in Europe (2022) [2]

Clean hydrogen for ammonia is only produced in Spain with 2,2 kt (0,11%) [2]. The Puertollano green hydrogen plant was not fully commissioned in 2022. In 2023, with the commissioning of the Puertollano green hydrogen plant, the clean hydrogen production for ammonia will be more than ten times higher with 37 kt/year.

Ammonia is mainly used for producing fertilizers such as urea and ammonium nitrate. Fertilizers account for around 80 % of today's global ammonia demand. Other markets include manufacturing of chemicals, plastics and textiles (acrylonitrile, melamine), the mining industry (low-density ammonium nitrate explosives, metals brightening processes), pharmaceuticals, refrigeration, waste treatment, and air treatment, such as abatement of nitrogen oxide (NO_x).

3.1.2.2 H₂ use for ammonia production: potential market.

According to IRENA, the worldwide production of ammonia was 183 Mt in 2020 and would reach 688 Mt in 2050 (see figure hereunder) [5]. Existing uses of ammonia would increase by 82% between 2020 and 2050, driven by population growth.

AL: N
ECCN: N

Figure 16: Expected ammonia demand up to 2050 for the 1.5°C scenario [5]

In Europe, fertilizer use of nitrogen is expected to decrease by 5,7% between 2021 and 2031 according to Fertilizers Europe [6]. New markets are expected for ammonia, such as transport fuel for maritime industry, hydrogen carrier and fuel for power generation. Figure 17 shows an overview of the potential roles of ammonia in the hydrogen economy, extracted from [5].

N
ECCN:
N
AL:

N
ECCN:
N
AL:

Figure 17: Potential roles of ammonia in the hydrogen economy [5]

Ammonia synthesis is almost exclusively generated by SMR of natural gas coupling with a Haber-Bosch unit in two steps: forming gas production (a mixture of hydrogen and nitrogen) and ammonia synthesis (from forming gas to ammonia). Low carbon ammonia could be obtained by replacing the grey hydrogen by green hydrogen or by capturing the emitted carbon. Producing one ton of ammonia requires around 180 kg of hydrogen. The average size of ammonia production unit in Europe is 600 kt of NH₃ per year, corresponding to a hydrogen need of 108 kt/year and 675 MWe of electrolyzer capacity. Nevertheless, replacing the SMR unit by electrolysis is not so easy because the SMR unit is highly integrated within the process and generates steam used for heat and electricity production on the site. It could be possible to replace only 10 to 15% of hydrogen needs without disturbing the steam balance of the site. Beyond, the site needs to be electrified and the investment cost is very high.

Consequently, there are four ways to decarbonize ammonia production:

- Replace 10% to 15% of hydrogen need. The electrolysis capacity would be around one hundred of megawatt, based on previous data. This solution would not allow to decarbonize completely the site. Seven projects under construction have been identified: first phases of Puertolanno (Spain) and Porsgrunn (Norway) projects, Sluiski (Netherlands), ottamarshein (France), Linz (Austria), Ludwigshafen (Germany) and Köln (Germany).
- Add a carbon capture unit.

- Electrify all the process and replace the steam reforming unit by electrolyzers (around 600 MW). The investment costs and the electricity need would be high. Three projects of this kind have been identified: Puertollano and Palos in Spain and Porsgrunn in Norway.
- New ammonia production sites. Four projects have been identified: Avilés and Sagunto in Spain, Lulea-Boden in Sweden and Aveiro in Portugal.

According to Hydrogen Europe [3], the announced consumption of clean hydrogen for ammonia production is about 2,1 Mt by 2030, of which 30% is located in Spain. Nevertheless, they underline a high risk of cancellation of these projects since one third are at a very early development stage. And only one quarter of planned clean ammonia production aims at producing fertilizers and other chemicals.

Indeed, ammonia could be used for other applications in the future and mainly for shipping (Figure 18). The following figure presents ammonia demand estimates for use as maritime fuel by 2050 from various sources. The lowest estimates is about 70 Mt/year for ammonia and the highest is about 950 Mt/year.

Figure 18: Ammonia demand estimates for use as maritime fuel by 2050 from various sources [5]

This differences between estimates can be explained by the fact that there is no consensus on the future fuel for maritime transport. Several options are possible: methanol, ammonia, LNG, e-methane. Moreover, IRENA states that new codes are required for ammonia as a maritime fuel.

Considering that European maritime fuel consumption represents 19% of worldwide maritime fuel consumption [7] [8], it can be assumed that the European ammonia demand for maritime transportation would be between 13 and 182 Mt/year in 2050. The corresponding hydrogen demand would be between 2 and 33 Mt/year in 2050.

3.1.3 Steel

3.1.3.1 H₂ use for steel industry: description and current use.

There are two classical routes for steel production: the Blast Furnace-Basic Oxygen Furnace (BF-BOF) route used to create new steel from iron ore and the Electric Arc Furnace (EAF) route used to recycle steel from scrap, see Figure 19.

Figure 19: Overview of the steelmaking process [9]

About 60% of total EU steel is produced via the BF-BOF production route. It is composed of the BF, where iron ore is reduced to cast iron using coke, and the BOF, where the hot metal is converted into steel. This route uses coal as the main carbon-bearing material and also to generate the high temperatures necessary to smelt iron ore. An EAF produces secondary steel by melting steel scrap with the heat generated by an electric arc, using additives to adjust the chemical composition of the steel. The availability of recycled steel limits EAF production.

There are 5 ways to decarbonize steel production:

1. H₂ as reducing agent in Direct Reduction of Iron (DRI) route. This option consists in a complete shift from BF-BOF route to DRI EAF route. In the DRI route, iron is directly reduced by a reducing gas (methane, hydrogen, syngas). Today DRI represents 5% of crude steel production [1]. In most of the case, the reducing agent is methane but the shift to hydrogen is possible and this could allow a decrease in carbon emissions.

AL: N
ECCN: N

Figure 20: DRI route (source: Grinhy Project)

N
ECCN:
N
AL:

2. Injection of H₂ in BF-BOF route, replacing a part of coke: this option allows a decrease of about 20% of carbon emissions [10]. There is no major modification of the process, but it is not a solution to carbon neutrality.
3. Carbon Capture and Use (CCU) to produce organic molecules.
4. H₂ as fuel in the downstream part of the process (reheating furnaces). This option concerns the EAF route for steel manufacturing from scrap. After the EAF step, reheating furnaces for metal sheets, billets and blooms are fed with natural gas and are responsible for the largest part of carbon emissions on those sites.
5. Co-electrolysis H₂+CO in BF-BOF route, replacing a part of coke.

Hydrogen is already used at steel annealing processes. Annealing is a heat treatment for processed steel to restore ductility. Hydrogen allows the prevention of oxidation during the process and increase the heat transfer of the inert atmosphere due to its higher heat transfer coefficient than most other gases. For this application, hydrogen is mostly supplied bulk or produced by alkaline electrolysis. For small sites, there is no incentive to shift to green hydrogen since the carbon emissions linked to hydrogen use are low.

Hydrogen for DRI in the iron and steel subsector represents 5,3 Mt worldwide. European use of hydrogen for DRI is quite small with 1,5 kt (0,03% of the worldwide use). It is concentrated in 3 countries (Austria, Sweden and Germany) and only produced by clean ways.

Figure 21: Hydrogen consumption for direct reduction iron

One DRI plant with a capacity of 2,5 Mt/year of steel would have a consumption of 120 kt of hydrogen per year, that corresponds to an electrolyzer capacity of 750 MW (supposing 50 kWhel/kg H₂ and 8000 functioning hours). If we consider one to three direct reduction plant per production sites, the needed capacity of electrolyzer is between 750 and 2250 MW. The resulting need in electricity is between 6 TWh/year and 18 TWh/year.

3.1.3.2 H₂ use for steel industry: potential market.

The different studies at EU scale [11] [12] [13] estimate a hydrogen demand for steel industry between 3 and 5 million tons of hydrogen in 2050. The European association of the steel industry, Eurofer, estimated the hydrogen demand in 2030 at 2,2 Mt. This estimation is made on the base of the announced project of shifting to hydrogen. We can suppose that the implementation of projects will be progressive and assume a hydrogen demand of 1 Mt in 2030, 2,2 Mt in 2035.

There are 27 production sites in Europe for 32 blast furnaces. Germany is the first European producer with 6 production sites. The following figure presents the map of EU steel production sites.

N
ECCN:
N
AL:

Map of EU steel production sites

- Blast Furnace & Basic Oxygen Furnace
- Blast Furnace only
- Basic Oxygen Furnace only

Figure 22: map of EU steel production sites [14]

In 2024, there are 6 steelmaking enterprises in Ukraine of which 5 are in operation.

3.1.4 Methanol

3.1.4.1 H₂ use for methanol production: description and current use.

Methanol (CH₃OH) is one of the four critical basic chemicals (alongside ethylene, propylene and ammonia) used to produce all other chemical products. Formaldehyde is the methanol largest-volume derivative, which is used to produce resins used by the construction, automotive and consumer goods industries. It is also used as a feedstock in the chemical industry for producing acetic acid which is essentially used for the production of polyester fibers and PET plastics. In addition, it is used as a fuel, pure or mixed.

Methanol can be produced from concentrated carbon sources, such as natural gas, coal, biomass or even captured CO₂ combined with green hydrogen. In Figure 23, extracted from Methanol Institute website [15], are shown feedstock and applications of methanol.

AL: N
ECCN: N

Figure 23: Feedstock and applications of methanol.

Nowadays, methanol is predominantly synthesized from the syngas using copper-based catalyst at operating pressures between 50 and 100 bar and operating temperatures between 200 and 300 °C, and involves the hydrogenation of CO and CO₂ and the Water Gas Shift Reaction (WGSR). E-methanol is methanol that is produced from renewable or decarbonised electricity. The e-methanol has a double advantage; it allows to store renewable electricity in chemical form and at the same time to produce a fully renewable product that can replace the fossil-derived one.

E-methanol is produced by means of CO₂ catalytic hydrogenation by means of the same reactions involved in the synthesis of methanol, but compared to the syngas to methanol process, the raw methanol produced in the synthesis of e-methanol process contains more water (hydrogenation of CO₂ introduces more water than the hydrogenation of CO).

Another approach is to produce both components of syngas, CO and H₂, through electrolysis, followed by conversion of the syngas to e-methanol as practiced for conventional methanol production. In this case the production of CO and H₂ can be carried out in a single step (see Annex 5 section 8.5).

In Europe, methanol can be blended with petrol up to 3%. The European methanol production is about 2 Mt/year and the European consumption is more than two times higher, between 5 and 5,5 Mt/year. More than the half of the European consumption is imported, mainly from Egypt, Trinidad and Tobago, and the United States.

Worldwide, 16 Mt of hydrogen is used for methanol production (around 130 kg hydrogen is required as feedstock per ton of methanol). European use represents 1,52% with 243 kt of hydrogen consumed per year. Methanol production is concentrated in 7 countries with Germany amounting for 62% of European hydrogen use for methanol production. Iceland is the only country with clean hydrogen use for methanol in 2022 (674 t/year).

Figure 24: Hydrogen consumption for methanol production.

3.1.4.2 H₂ use for methanol production: potential market.

Methanol is produced by a catalytic reaction between hydrogen and carbon dioxide (or carbon monoxide) in a steam methane-reforming unit (Figure 25, on the left). To decarbonize the methanol production, two options are possible:

- Bio-methanol: the natural gas is replaced by bio-methane (biomass gasification);
- E-methanol: the SMR unit is replaced by an electrolyzer. Nevertheless, a source of carbon has to be found. That is why, methanol with low-carbon H₂ as to be coupled with a CO₂ capture. (Figure 25, on the right)

Figure 25: Methanol production: traditional route (left), with CO₂ Capture unit (right)

According to the European Hydrogen Observatory [2], there are 12 methanol production sites in Europe with an average hydrogen use of 20 kt/year. Considering, 8000 operating hours and an efficiency of 50 kWh/kg_{H₂}, the average electrolyser capacity would be about 125 MW.

According to the No-regret Hydrogen Study [13], the hydrogen demand for methanol production (excluding methanol for e-fuels), would be about 300 kt/year in 2035 and will remain stable until 2050.

N
ECCN:
N
AL:

3.1.5 Other chemicals uses

In 2022, the hydrogen production capacity for other chemicals is about 1 Mt/year. By-product hydrogen represents 347 kt/year. It is assumed that by-product hydrogen wouldn't be replaced by green hydrogen as it is a by-product. Consequently, only the reforming and water electrolysis capacity production are considered. This later is about 671 kt/year.

Figure 26: H₂ Consumption for other chemicals (2022)

Focusing only on reforming and water electrolysis production, 4 countries represent 80% of the production capacity: the Netherlands (35%), the United Kingdom (22%), Germany (12%) and Hungary (10%) [2].

Figure 27: hydrogen production capacity other chemicals without by-products capacities

The sub-sector “other chemicals” covers a wide range of molecules such as hydrogen peroxide, Toluene Diisocyanate (TDI), hexamethylenediamine. Hydrogen needs for the production of these molecules are lower than thus for ammonia or methanol production. The average hydrogen need for hydrogen peroxide or TDI is estimated at 900 kg/h, that is 45 MW of electrolyze (8 000 operating hours and efficiency of 50 kWh/kg).

3.1.6 Other industrial uses

There are other traditional industrial uses, with little unit size:

- Glass industry: Hydrogen is used as a getter gas to prevent oxidation over the tin baths used in the float glass manufacturing process. For this application, hydrogen is supplied bulk or produced by alkaline electrolysis. The volumes engaged are negligible in comparison to the carbon emissions due to combustion during the manufacturing process of float glass. The European market is estimated at 7 kt in Europe with an average electrolyzer capacity of 0,5 MW.
- Semiconductor industry: Hydrogen is used as an inerting agent for the wafer production and a carrier gas for thin-film deposition. It is supplied bulk or produced by alkaline electrolysis. The European market size is estimated to 5 kt/year.
- Food industry: polyols production (7 kt/year).

3.1.7 Emerging applications

Germany consumes more than the half of European hydrogen used for mobility, blending in natural gas pipelines, e-fuels, residential heat and power generation.

Figure 28: hydrogen use for emerging applications.

3.1.7.1 Transport

Transport sector is a major source of emissions due to its current heavy reliance on fossil fuels. Reducing emissions will require substantial changes in propulsion systems and the choice of fuels that the transport sector relies on.

The preferable path to low CO₂ emissions has become clear for some but not all transport modes. Electrification is a viable option for rail and light-duty road transport (cars, small trucks), assuming that the electricity comes from renewable sources. In the case of rail transport, the use of electricity is already widespread, especially for passenger transport. For other transport modes, however, the optimal pathway has yet to become clear. Road freight transport, aviation and shipping are significant energy users and CO₂ emitters, and reducing their emissions will be a challenge.

According to the report “Reaching zero with renewables” delivered by IRENA [16], the emissions impact in 2017 of these subsectors are presented in Table 1.

Table 1: Emissions impact of transport in 2017

	Transport-related emissions (%)	Global energy-related emissions (%)
Road freight transport	27	6
Aviation	11	3
Shipping	10	2

The options available to reduce direct emissions in these three harder-to-decarbonise sub-sectors are presented below [16]:

- Road freight:
 1. Battery Electric Vehicles (BEV): use electric motors powered by a battery pack, charged with renewable electricity. This option is already mature for light-duty vehicles and yearly sales are increasing.
 2. Fuel Cell Electric Vehicle (FCEV): use electricity produced by fuel cells powered by compressed (green) hydrogen. For light-duty vehicles, BEV are more competitive than FCEV. For heavy-duty vehicles, hydrogen is an emerging option. In both cases, the refueling infrastructure have to be installed. More details in Annex 4, section 8.4.1.
 3. Advanced biofuels: use biomass-based fuel substitutes, such as biodiesels and renewable diesels. The feedstock availability is a potential limitation.
- Aviation:
 1. Biofuel jet: use fuels produced from sustainably sourced biomass
 2. E-fuels: use synthetic fuels produced from cleanly sourced CO₂ and green hydrogen
 3. Battery-powered aircraft: use propulsion systems powered by batteries charged with renewable electricity
- Shipping:
 1. Advanced biofuels: use biomass-based fuels such as biodiesel, renewable diesel, bio-methanol, bio-fuel oil and liquefied biogas
 2. E-fuels: use green hydrogen or synthetic fuels such as green methanol, ammonia and methanol (more detailed in Annex 4, section 8.4.2 and 8.4.3)

An overview of selected renewables energy carriers, extracted from [16] is presented in Figure 29.

Figure 29: Overview of selected renewables energy carriers.

In 2022, 3,5 kt of hydrogen has been used for mobility in Europe. With the Alternative Fuel Infrastructure Regulation (AFIR) (more details in section 4.1.2.2), more than 700 hydrogen refueling stations will have to be introduced in European roads by 2030 [17]. With a minimal capacity of 1-ton H₂/day, the hydrogen demand would be around 260 kt/year for road transportation uses by 2035.

3.1.7.2 E-fuels

The European consumption of kerosene was about 48,3 Mt in 2019 [18]. The European consumption represented 15% of the worldwide consumption. Aviation's sectoral share of global CO₂ emissions is about 2,5% [19]. Global aviation CO₂ emissions have doubled between 1990 and 2019 [19] and air traffic is expected to double by 2050.

The actors of the aviation sector have agreed to follow 3 main levers for action:

- 1) Operating improvements linked to the optimization of trajectories
- 2) Improving the technologies of the aircrafts to reduce their fuel consumption
- 3) Increasing the use of Sustainable Aviation Fuel (SAF) along with carbon compensation mechanisms

SAF are liquid non-fossil hydrocarbons that have the required properties to be added to traditional fuel blends, without requiring any modification on the corresponding engine (drop-in). SAF include biofuels coming from various processes accepted by the ASTM (American Society for Testing and Materials) and the electro-based fuels produced by Power to Liquid (PtL) processes. To be described as a SAF, a given fuel must have a carbon footprint reduced by 70% by comparison to a traditional fossil fuel (reference being 84 g CO₂eq/MJ).

According to the European Union Aviation Safety Agency (EASA), current SAF supply remains low at less than 0,05%. The European Commission aims at increasing gradually shares of SAF, from 2% in 2025 to 63% in 2050. This will correspond to 2,3 million tons of SAF in 2030, 14,8 million tons of SAF by 2040 and 28,6 Mt by 2050 [19].

The Hydroprocessed Esters and Fatty Acids (HEFA) / Hydrotreated Vegetable Oil (HVO) pathway is the only available and running industrially pathway. Other pathways are envisaged:

- Alcohol to jet: fermentation of processed lignocellulosic feedstocks or sugar and starch crops.
- Biomass gasification + Fisher Tropsch: not yet available on a commercial scale within the EU.
- Power & biomass to liquid: an electrolyzer is used in the previous pathway to add hydrogen and improve the carbon conversion ratio.
- Power to liquid: hydrogen produced by electrolysis is synthetized with CO₂ into syngas. The syngas is then processed into fuel by a Fisher Tropsch reactor.

The following figure presents the SAF approved production pathways with feedstock and Technological Readiness Level (TRL) for each.

AL: N
ECCN: N

Production pathway	Feedstocks ³⁰	Certification name (blending limit)	TRL
Biomass Gasification + Fischer-Tropsch (Gas+FT)	Energy crops, lignocellulosic biomass, solid waste	FT-SPK ³¹ (up to 50%)	7-8
Hydroprocessed Esters and Fatty Acids (HEFA)	Vegetable and animal fat	HEFA-SPK (up to 50%)	8-9
Direct Sugars to Hydrocarbons (DSHC)	Conventional sugars, lignocellulosic sugars	HFS-SIP ³² (up to 10%)	7-8 or 5 ³³
Biomass Gasification + FT with Aromatics	Energy crops, lignocellulosic biomass, solid waste	FT-SPK/A ³⁴ (up to 50%)	6-7
Alcohols to Jet (AtJ)	Sugar, starch crops, lignocellulosic biomass	ATJ-SPK (up to 50%)	7-8
Catalytic Hydrothermolysis Jet (CHJ)	Vegetable and animal fat	CHJ or CH-SK ³⁵ (up to 50%)	6
HEFA from algae	Microalgae oils	HC-HEFA-SPK ³⁶ (up to 10%)	5
FOG Co-processing	Fats, oils, and greases	FOG (up to 5 %)	-
FT Co-processing	Fischer-Tropsch (FT) biocrude	FT (up to 5 %)	-

Figure 30: SAF approved production pathways [19]

Due to feedstock availability, SAF production will necessarily be based on several routes. The development of SAF would require 104 to 250 plants by 2050 according to EASA.

The following figure, Figure 31, presents the estimated SAF supply by ReFuelEU and the corresponding hydrogen needs, deduced for each pathway.

Figure 31: ReFuelEU modelled SAF supply per production pathway in the EU27 and associated H₂ needs¹

In 2040, 2,21 Mt of hydrogen would be required and in 2050 7,31 Mt of hydrogen, corresponding to 110 to 365 TWh of electricity.

¹ Conversion ratios for H₂ needs extracted from [80] [80] [72]

3.1.7.3 Industrial heat

At European level, industrial heat is mainly supply by natural gas. Each industry and process have a need for a specific temperature. Agora Energiewende distinguishes low temperature needs (less than 100°C), medium temperature needs (100 to 500 °C) and high temperature needs (above 500°C) [13].

Figure 32: Natural gas final energy consumption for 2017 in the EU industry sector by application temperature.

Currently, more than 85% of industrial heat is consumed in iron and steel, chemicals and cement. Around 95% of the high-temperature heat is currently provided by the combustion of fossil fuels or combustible by-products.

Working temperatures for selected renewables heat technologies and temperature requirement of selected industries, extracted from the report “Green Hydrogen for Industry” [20], are presented in Figure 33.

Figure 33: Working temperatures for selected renewables heat technologies and temperature requirement of selected industries.

Low temperature uses can easily be decarbonized using heat-pumps. For higher temperature electrification with other power-to-heat options (resistance furnace, infrared heater, induction furnace, electric arc furnace, plasma heating and microwave and radio heaters) seems to be the better choice due to a better efficiency than hydrogen as a fuel.

Hydrogen as a fuel would be used only for hardly to electrify applications and will come at the end, after the process electrification. Even if, one of the advantages of hydrogen is that it involve minimal redesign in the industrial process, considering the advantages of electric heating (capacity for precise temperature regulation, low maintenance costs and given that the performance factor of high-temperature heat from electric heating is at the very least comparable to burning hydrogen from electrolysis) it should be considered as the first choice before green hydrogen.

Consequently, until 2030-2040 hydrogen for industrial heat would be negligible.

3.1.8 Summary

According to hydrogen uses described in section 3.1, the green hydrogen demand can be estimated between 5,7 and 6,4 Mt in 2035. The two main uses would be SAF and the steel industry with respectively 2,2 Mt. The following figure presents the estimated demand breakdown according to applications. These estimates are only indicative as forecasts are subject to considerable uncertainty.

Figure 34: European green hydrogen demand estimates (2035)

The following figure presents the electrolyzer average unit size for each hydrogen uses. Most important traditional hydrogen uses are requiring average unit sizes over 100 MW (ammonia, refining, methanol, steel). New emerging uses are not presented here because the average unit sizes of these applications are not known yet. In the context of the NPHyCo project, with a 45 MW electrolyzer, only smaller applications should be targeted such as other chemicals or new uses such as transport or SAF. Regarding the road transportation, the average size of refueling station should be around 1 to 2 tons of hydrogen per day that is an equivalent electrolyzer capacity of 2 to 4 MW. Nevertheless, the hydrogen production can be located on-site with small electrolyzer (2 – 4 MW) or centralized with bigger electrolyzer, from 20 to 100 MW. In the case of centralization, hydrogen have to be transported with tube trailers or pipelines.

Figure 35: Electrolyser average unit size vs number of sites in Europe

*other industry: semiconductor, flat glass, metal treatment, etc. The number of sites is indicative.

N
ECCN:
N
AL:

4 Required infrastructures for a competitive, realistic hydrogen market.

Expected volumes of renewable hydrogen produce in Europe by 2035 are very important (6 Mt according to section 3.1, more than 10 Mt according to RePowerEU targets). This deployment will face several challenges that are detailed in the next sections, among others:

- Regulatory frameworks and standards: the European regulatory framework is quite new (detailed in section 4.1) and evolving rapidly. A changing regulatory framework can hinder the hydrogen deployment because of uncertain environment for investors.
- Electricity needs for electrolysis: 10 Mt of hydrogen is equivalent to an electricity consumption of 480 TWh/year (detailed in section 4.2). This means that new renewable plants and grid reinforcement will be needed to ensure a renewable hydrogen production.
- Massive hydrogen storage: if hydrogen is produced with renewable energy such as solar or wind, there will be a need for massive hydrogen storage to deal with intermittency and seasonality of renewable energies (detailed in section 4.2.2).
- Hydrogen infrastructure: hydrogen production, massive storages and hydrogen consumption will not take place at the same location. Hydrogen infrastructure have to be developed to ensure a harmonized deployment of renewable hydrogen (detailed in section 4.3)

4.1 Facing the challenge of H₂ European production

4.1.1 A regulatory framework under construction, chronological evolution

The regulatory framework regarding hydrogen production, use and storage is under construction and is evolving rapidly. From a chronological point of view, the main steps are the following:

- **2020: the European Commission adopted the European Strategy on Hydrogen [21].** This later sets a target of 6 GW of electrolysis in 2024 and 40 GW in 2030. In parallel, the European Commission sets up the European Clean Hydrogen Alliance (ECHA) to support the large-scale deployment of clean hydrogen technologies by 2030². This Alliance identified a pipeline of more than 750 viable hydrogen projects.
- **2021: the European Commission presented the Fit-for-55 package** with the objective of reducing emissions by at least 55% compared to 1990 level, by the end of the decade. This legislative package adopted or revised at least 12 legislatives policies related to hydrogen (following figure from hydrogen observatory³).

² « European Clean Hydrogen Alliance - European Commission ».

³ « Observatory Reports | European Hydrogen Observatory ».

Hydrogen related legislations in Fit for 55 package	
EU Emissions Trading System (ETS)	Alternative Fuels Infrastructure Regulation (AFIR)
Effort Sharing Regulation	ReFuel EU Aviation Regulation
CO ₂ emissions standards for cars and vans	FuelEU Maritime Regulation
Carbon Border Adjustment Mechanism (CBAM)	Energy Performance of Buildings Directive
Renewable Energy Directive	Energy Taxation Directive
Energy Efficiency Directive	Hydrogen and gas markets decarbonisation package

Figure 36: Legislative policies adopted or revised in the Fit for 55 package and related to hydrogen [2]

The revision of several legislatives policies is still in progress. In the next section the main influencing directives and regulations are detailed.

- **2022: the Commissions adopted the REPowerEU** plan aiming at decreasing the European dependence to Russia. The plan sets the ambition to produce 10 million tonnes and import 10 million tonnes of renewable hydrogen in the EU by 2030 (this corresponds to 60 GW of electrolyzers each, considering 8.000 operating hours and an electrical consumption of 48 kWh/kgH₂). The aim is to accelerate the uptake of renewable hydrogen, ammonia and other derivatives in hard-to-decarbonise sectors, such as transport and energy-intensive industrial processes.
- **2023: creation of the European Hydrogen Bank** [22]. It is a financing instrument to support the hydrogen deployment. It is based on 4 pillars of action: domestic pillar (support hydrogen production in Europe with auctions), international pillar (support to hydrogen imports), transparency and coordination, existing financing instruments. In November 2023 the first domestic auctions were launched. The successful projects were selected in April 2024: 7 renewable hydrogen projects across Europe with a funding of 720 million €.

AL: N
ECCN: N

4.1.2 Focus on revised directives and regulations in Fit for 55 package.

As mentioned before, the Fit-for-55 package includes the revision of several legislations. Among them, the European Hydrogen Observatory identified 12 legislations related to hydrogen that are presented in Figure 37. Here the most impacting of them are detailed: the Renewable Energy Directive (RED), the Alternative Fuels Infrastructure Regulation, ReFuel UE Aviation and the Hydrogen and gas markets decarbonisation.

Hydrogen related legislations in Fit for 55 package	
EU Emissions Trading System (ETS)	Alternative Fuels Infrastructure Regulation (AFIR)
Effort Sharing Regulation	ReFuel EU Aviation Regulation
CO ₂ emissions standards for cars and vans	FuelEU Maritime Regulation
Carbon Border Adjustment Mechanism (CBAM)	Energy Performance of Buildings Directive
Renewable Energy Directive	Energy Taxation Directive
Energy Efficiency Directive	Hydrogen and gas markets decarbonisation package

Figure 37: View of the 12 legislations related to hydrogen identified and highlight on the ones that are detailed in the next sections

Note that a revision of a legislation takes time between the first proposal of the Commission to the Parliament and the Council, the agreement of the Parliament and the Council and final adoption of the text.

4.1.2.1 Renewable Energy Directive II and III

The Renewable Energy Directive EU/2018/2001 (RED II) sets the overall EU target for renewable energy sources consumption by 2030 to 32%. Regarding hydrogen and Renewable Fuels of Non-Biological Origin (RFNBO), two delegated acts were adopted in February 2023. The first one, Delegated act 2023/1184, sets out detailed rules for the production of renewable liquid and gaseous transport fuels of non-biological origin:

- **Renewability:** electricity should be limited to renewable energy sources only
- **Temporal correlation:** RFNBO is produced during the same calendar month as the renewable electricity until December 2029. From 1 January, the temporal correlation is reduced to one hour.
- **Geographical correlation:** the production and power plants should be located in the same bidding zone.
- **Additionality:** the installation generating renewable electricity came into operation not earlier than 36 months before the installation producing the RFNBO and has not received support in the form of operating aid or investment aid.

These three criterias have not to be met if the average renewable electricity share of the bidding zone exceeds 90% in the previous calendar year. It may be counted as renewable if it does not exceed the proportion of renewable electricity in the bidding zone. No Member State falls under this case. If grid emission intensity of the bidding zone is under 18g CO₂e/MJ, it may count as renewable if hydrogen producers conclude one or more renewable Power Purchase Agreements (PPA) fulfilling temporal and geographical correlation. Sweden is the only Member State fulfilling this case. France (19.6 g CO₂e/MJ), Finland (22.9 g CO₂ e/MJ) and Denmark (27.1 g CO₂e/MJ) could reach this emission intensity. [12] Electricity is also considered fully renewable at times where the production of RFNBO supports the integration of renewable power generation and reduces the need for redispatching.

The second delegated act 2023/1185, establish a minimum threshold for greenhouse gas emissions savings and specify a methodology for assessing Greenhouse Gas (GHG) savings. The threshold is set at 70% below a fossil fuel comparator of **94 gCO₂ eq/MJ, equivalent to 3,38-ton CO₂ eq/ton H₂.**

Note that even if hydrogen produced with nuclear electricity is below 3,38-ton CO₂ eq/ton H₂, it does not fulfill the renewability criteria.

The aforementioned RED II has been revised in October 2023 and named RED III ((UE) 2023/2413). The overall EU target for renewable energy sources consumption become 42,5%.

4.1.2.2 AFIR – Alternative Fuel Infrastructure Regulation (UE 2023/1804)

Member states have to ensure the construction of one gaseous hydrogen refueling station every 200 km on the TEN-T core network by the end of 2030, as well as one hydrogen refueling station in every urban node. The supply capacity has to be of one ton of hydrogen.

N
ECCN:
AL: N

4.1.2.3 ReFuelEU Aviation

The ReFuelEU Aviation has been adopted in October 2023 and lays down harmonized rules on the uptake and supply of SAF. The regulation defines shares of SAF at airports: minimum share of 2% of SAF from 2025, 6% of SAF from 2030, 20% of SAF from 2035, 35% from 2040, 42% from 2045 and 70% from 2050.

4.1.2.4 Hydrogen and decarbonized gas market package

The hydrogen and decarbonized gas market package refers to the revision of the Gas Directive 2009/73/EC and Gas Regulation (EC) 715/2009. The revision is still under progress: after a first set of proposals from the Commission in July 2021, the European Parliament adopted a resolution in April 2024. The final text is not yet published.

4.1.3 European taxonomy

The EU taxonomy is a classification system that helps companies and investors identify environmentally sustainable economic activities. The EU Taxonomy Navigator website gives value for different activities. For hydrogen production the threshold is 3-ton CO₂ eq/ton H₂.

4.2 Challenges for the electricity grid

4.2.1 Important need of new generating capacity

Most European countries do not have an electricity mix carbon-free enough to produce low-carbon hydrogen from electrolyzers powered by the network (see Figure 38). And even worse, for more than half of the European countries, the CO₂ content of such a hydrogen would be higher than if it was produced by a SMR.

Considering the RED II threshold, only Iceland, Sweden, Norway, France, Luxembourg and Finland are able to produce hydrogen from electrolyzers powered by the network with a CO₂ content lower than the RED II threshold [3]. In other countries, hydrogen producers can use the grid and buy Guarantee of Origin (GO). GOs are a certificate that provide evidence that a given share or quantity of energy was produced from renewable sources. The other way is to sign a PPA with a renewable producer.

AL: N
ECCN: N

Figure 38: Carbon intensity of hydrogen produced from electrical grid, compared to selected benchmarks [3]

Thus, in order to reach the objective described in REPowerEU plan that target 10 Mtons of renewable H₂ produced in EU in 2030, an increase of low-carbon electricity capacity is needed. The supply of low-carbon and cheap electricity is one of the main concerns from the point of view of manufacturers.

If an electricity consumption of 50 kWh/kg H₂ PCI is considered for the electrolyzer, 10 Mtons of H₂ per year at the European scale would need 500 TWh of low-carbon electricity. This new energy consumption represents about 19% of the total amount of electricity produced in the 28 countries of EU in 2022 (~2642 TWh) according to Eurostat data [18].

Nevertheless, it should be noticed again that currently RED III does not consider nuclear as a possible source to produce renewable hydrogen.

Additionally, to the challenge of electricity decarbonization owing to either renewable energies or nuclear power plants, the grid should be reinforced due to new capacities. In Europe, locations with a very significant potential for renewable energies have been identified. To be able to exploit this potential, modifications on the electrical grid transportation network will be needed. Besides, using these renewable energies potential leads to several considerations to take into account. The first one is the fact that renewable energies are intermittent whereas the needs in hydrogen are rather constant. Another one is the fact that places with abundant renewable energies potential are not necessarily places with a significant hydrogen consumption. Thus, options to solve these issues include the development of massive storages, the deployment of a hydrogen transportation network and reinforcement of electricity grids in the case of PPA. The use of hydrogen storage is also a solution to better use the electricity surplus due to renewable energies or nuclear power plants. Thus, H₂ can be produced during excess electricity periods and not during peaks of consumption that could lead to the startup of gas turbines. Furthermore, having a well-organized hydrogen transportation network would

ECCN: N
AL: N

probably decrease the needs in electricity grid reinforcement as it offers the possibility to put the electrolyzers not at the same location as hydrogen is consumed because it is often located where the electricity consumption is already huge.

In the next section, a focus is made on technical solutions to store hydrogen massively and sections 4.3 and 4.4 are dedicated to the hydrogen transportation and distribution network.

4.2.2 Options to massive storage of hydrogen

Commonly used hydrogen storage systems are above ground hydrogen compressed storage. This later is well suited for a single production site. Nevertheless, the storage capacity is limited for massive storage at EU scale.

One interesting option is to store hydrogen underground. Among the possible solutions, there are:

- Depleted gas reservoirs: containing initially hydrocarbons then repurposed to store natural gas. They are largely used for natural gas storage in Europe, but they offer a limited injection/extraction cycle. Hydrogen cycling affects integrity and stability of reservoirs. [23]
- Aquifers: Porous reservoir rock containing water which can be expelled by injecting gas under pressure but as it is porous, there can be hydrogen diffusion.
- Salt caverns: Salt rock dissolved by injecting water to dig a cavity. This solution offers several advantages: rock salt inert and impermeable to hydrogen and they offer flexible injection/extraction cycles that can be used to answer to both daily and seasonal needs. [23]

The most promising solution are salt caverns. Hydrogen would then be stored at 300 to 1.800 meters under the ground. The pressure would be 80 to 300 bars. Salt caverns are already used in the United States (Clemens since 1983 and Moss Bluff since 2007) and in the United Kingdom (Teesside since 1972) to store hydrogen. In France, the European Project Hypster is in progress and the salt cavern should be in operation in late 2024⁴.

Article [24] assessed European subsurface salt structures for hydrogen storage in terms of size, land eligibility and storage capacity. The following map presents the location of salt caverns in Europe.

⁴ « Press release September 2023 – Inauguration of the HyPSTER project*, first demonstration facility for renewable hydrogen storage in salt caverns | HyPSTER ».

storage (1. Alsace Basin; 2. Bresse Basin; 3. Greoux Basin; 4. Valence Basin; 5. Lower Rhine Basin; 6. Hessen Werra Basin; 7. Sub-Hercynian Basin; 8. Lausitz Basin; 9. Leba Salt; 10. Fore-Sudetic Monocline; 11. Carpathian Foredeep; 12. Lublin Trough; 13. Ocnele Mari; 14. Cardona Saline Formation; 15. Pripyat Basin; 16. Cheshire Basin; 17. UK Permian Zechstein Basin; 18. Larnie Salt Field; 19. Wessex Basin).⁴

Figure 39: Map of European salt deposits and salt structures as a result of suitability assessment for underground hydrogen storage.

Figure 40 presents the estimated salt cavern storage in Europe. Total salt cavern storage potential constitutes 84.8 PWh_{H2}. Germany has the highest potential with 42% of the estimated capacity, mainly located near the shore.

Figure 40: Total salt cavern storage potential in European countries [24]

According to [25] and [26] the capital investment of hydrogen storage in salt cavern is around 32 €/kg. This is much less than above ground hydrogen compressed storage, estimated to 700 €/kg (this cost is strongly influenced by the hydrogen pressure).

The development of massive hydrogen storage is linked to the development of a hydrogen transportation infrastructure. Hydrogen can be transported either by trucks in gaseous or liquid form or by pipelines. For overseas transportation hydrogen carriers will be used as ammonia, methanol, or liquid organic carriers.

4.3 Challenges for hydrogen transport

Main delivery chains for hydrogen are Compressed Hydrogen (CGH₂), Liquefied Hydrogen (LH₂), Ammonia (NH₃), Methanol (MeOH), and Liquid Organic Hydrogen Carriers (LOHC). CGH₂ and LH₂ are well suited for on shore supply while ammonia, methanol and LOHC would be mainly used for overseas transportation.

According to JRC [27], the most cost-effective way to transport hydrogen depends on distance, amount, final use, and whether the infrastructure already exists.

4.3.1 Compressed hydrogen

Currently, CGH₂ is the preferred option for storing and transporting hydrogen. This packaging option has a low technological complexity; however, it also has a low density. This low density represents a challenge when delivering large amounts of hydrogen.

The most commonly used technologies for the compression of hydrogen are based in mechanical compression and include reciprocating, diaphragm and centrifugal compressors. Once compressed, hydrogen must be stored in a suitable system able to withstand the storage pressure and with materials compatible with hydrogen under those storage conditions.

Nowadays, compressed hydrogen is mostly transported by road, using systems known as Multiple Element Gas Containers (MEGCs) or tube trailers. Tube trailers capacity is between 300 kg (at 200 bars) to 1000 kg (500 bars) [26]. CGH₂ can also be transported by pipelines (detailed in section 4.4).

Once arrived at the consumption site, the CGH₂ should be delivered to the local storage system of the end-user (except in the case of hydrogen delivered by pipeline).

4.3.2 Liquefied Hydrogen

At atmospheric pressure, hydrogen reaches the liquid state at 20 K (-253 °C). Under these conditions, the hydrogen density is 2,3 times higher than the density of compressed hydrogen at 500 bar and normal conditions. This is the main reason why this packaging option, despite the technical and economic challenges involving the use of cryogenic temperatures, may be preferable to the use of CGH₂.

The hydrogen produced is liquefied by means of liquefaction plants and stored in cryogenic tanks.

Liquefied Hydrogen (LH₂) transport is currently limited, with few exceptions, to road transport by means of insulated tanks placed on top of trailers (tankers). The typical transport capacity is about 4000 kg H₂/truck.

AL: N
ECCN: N

Due to the high cost of liquefaction compared to compression, LH₂ is more expensive to transport by road than CGH₂ over short distances. However, as LH₂ trucks can carry more hydrogen than CGH₂ trucks in terms of density, the unit transportation cost is significantly lower. As a result, as distances increase, LH₂ trucks begin to outperform to CGH₂ trucks.

The last step in the LH₂ delivery chain is usually the regasification of the hydrogen, which could be provided directly to the demand point.

4.3.2.1 Hydrogen carriers

For overseas transportation, hydrogen carriers are envisaged to overcome limitation of CGH₂ (low density) and LH₂ (cryogenic temperature). Ammonia, Methanol and LOHC are potential hydrogen carriers.

- **Ammonia**

Ammonia (NH₃) is a chemical commodity traded worldwide that is usually produced via the Haber-Bosch process, reacting hydrogen and nitrogen. The ammonia produced is usually stored in large cryogenic tanks. The use of ships, trains and trucks for transporting ammonia is well-established. Ammonia is also transported in pressurized liquid form through pipelines over distances which can span thousands of kilometers.

Ammonia cracking is an endothermic process and can be regarded as the reverse of the synthesis reaction. Purification of the produced hydrogen has to be guaranteed and purification steps have to be implemented in the process.

- **Methanol**

Methanol is a chemical commodity which production is based on syngas (a mixture of carbon monoxide or dioxide and hydrogen) used as a synthesis precursor and obtained from fossil fuels.

Large-scale storage of methanol is usually performed in carbon steel or austenitic stainless-steel tanks much like flammable oil products such as currently used fuels. Special care should be given to safety, since methanol is a flammable volatile liquid, whose vapours have a higher flammability range than gasoline.

Methanol transport can be performed using ships, trains, and trucks suitable for transporting hazardous chemicals. The reference process for obtaining hydrogen back from methanol is the steam reforming.

- **Liquid Organic Hydrogen Carriers**

Liquid Organic Hydrogen Carriers (LOHC) are molecules able to release or accept hydrogen under specific temperature and pressure conditions.

Hydrogenation of aromatic hydrocarbons is a standard process often used in the chemical industry, for packing hydrogen.

LOHC can be stored in large quantities at ambient conditions in double-walled containers, as used for crude oil or diesel. Due to its similarities with crude oil or chemical products, LOHC will be transported using the same transport solutions as the ones used for those products.

The dehydrogenation of LOHCs has a high energy demand as the strong C–H bond has to be broken. Typically, a dehydrogenation temperature ranging from 150-400°C is needed to reach reasonable hydrogen release rates.

4.4 Challenges for the gas infrastructure

4.4.1 Different grid configurations are envisaged.

The decarbonation of gas grids with biomethane or hydrogen leads to new challenges for the gas transporters and distributors. The gas grid becomes more and more decentralized with new little gas producers that have impacts on the grid management (pressure, gas quality, etc.). Three grid configurations are envisaged to transport hydrogen by pipelines:

- Methane (with Carbon Capture Utilization and Storage (CCUS), biomethane and synthetic methane);
- Blending hydrogen and methane.
- Dedicated hydrogen grid.

In Figure 41, extracted from the ENTSOG 2050 Roadmap for Gas Grids [28], is presented the hybrid system proposed in order to reduce the costs of the energy transition and facilitate the decarbonisation of the gas sector.

Figure 41: Gas/electricity hybrid energy system.

The first grid configuration is the current situation with more biomethane and methanation of hydrogen before injection in the gas grid. The second configuration is based on transporting blends of hydrogen with methane to an acceptable threshold for appliances (20% of volume). Hydrogen is then produced by electrolysis, reforming of natural gas with CCUS or pyrolysis. At distribution network level, some pipelines could be dedicated to hydrogen. The third configuration is based on 100% dedicated hydrogen networks. In this case, new transmission pipelines will be built or repurposed.

The following figure, Figure 42, presents the three configurations of gas grids: methane grid configuration (on the left with 0% hydrogen), blending hydrogen and methane grid configuration (on the left with 20% of hydrogen in volume), hydrogen grid configuration (dedicated grids).

Figure 42: Methane and hydrogen gas grid configurations [CEA]

The three configurations will coexist. To ensure their integration, conversion services like methanation (H_2 to CH_4), methane reformer (CH_4 to H_2), blending or separation via membranes are required, as presented in Figure 43.

Figure 43: Methane and hydrogen conversion services [28]

Processes of methanation and separation are presented in Annex 2, section 8.2.

4.4.2 European hydrogen backbone initiative

The European Hydrogen Backbone (EHB) initiative groups 31 European network operators. It published the European Hydrogen Backbone report in April 2022 [29] and updated in November 2023.

The aim of the report is to present the EHB vision of the future pan-European hydrogen transport infrastructure.

The EHB initiative calculated that in order to transport 10 Mt of H₂ across Europe, 5 large scales pipeline corridors are needed. This calculation is based on the fact that a hydrogen pipeline can transport about 65 TWh of H₂ per year according to a previous study of EHB and on the fact that 10 Mt of H₂ represents 330 TWh LHV [29].

The corridors are located in such a way that the strong renewable energies potential locations that could produce quite large quantities of H₂ could be linked to modest renewable energies potential locations that could gather a lot of H₂ consumers. Thus, there would be corridors coming from Southern and Eastern European countries where solar resources could be used to produce H₂ owing to electrolysis. There would be also corridors coming from North, Baltic and Mediterranean Seas where the wind potential is high. The idea is to decarbonize activities using hydrogen with high carbon content along the corridor. The two following figures present the transport infrastructure maps for 2030 and 2040 [29].

ECCN: N

AL: N

Figure 44: EHB network map 2030.

© 2022 Guidehouse

- | | | |
|-------------------|------------------|--|
| Pipelines | Storages | Other |
| — Repurposed | ▲ Salt cavern | • City, for orientation purposes |
| — New | ● Aquifer | ● Energy hub / Offshore (wind) hydrogen production |
| — Subsea | ● Depleted field | ⊕ Existing or planned gas-import-terminal |
| — Import / Export | ● Rock cavern | |

Figure 45: EHB network map 2040.

The 5 corridors are described in Annex 3 of the report, section 8.3.

The corridor from Southern European countries became more concrete with H2MED project formalization. H2MED would make it possible to transport hydrogen produced in Portugal and Spain from Barcelona to Germany through the port of Fos-sur-Mer/Marseille. An agreement was signed between the Portuguese, Spanish and French gas transportation network operators REN, Enagás, GRTgaz and Teréga end of 2022 to collaborate on this project. The feasibility studies should end in 2024 and the commissioning is planned in 2030. H2MED would allow the transportation of up to 2 Mtons per year of low-carbon H₂, i.e. 10% of the REPowerEU target.

ECCN: N

AL: N

5 Comparison between nuclear H₂ with other technologies

This section aims to resume the main paths to produce hydrogen in such a way that the nuclear hydrogen and in particular the results obtained in deliverable D3.2 [30] can be replaced in their context and compared with other technologies.

5.1 Different H₂ colors

The H₂ color classification is not a standard defined in any regulatory framework. Nevertheless, it is commonly used to define hydrogen categories that depends on the production process and on the energy source that are used to produce hydrogen.

Even if there could be slight differences in the classification that can be found in the literature, the classification given in Figure 46, extracted from [31] is commonly agreed on.

Figure 46: Hydrogen color classification.

Grey hydrogen is produced either by SMR or by coal gasification supplied either by natural gas and water or by coal and air without CCUS. These two processes are more described in section 5.3.1.

Blue hydrogen is obtained when a CCUS is coupled to SMR process. It is more described in section 5.3.2.

Turquoise hydrogen is also based on fossil fuel but owing to Pyrolysis process which is less mature. Therefore, it will not be described further.

Depending on the electricity source, electrolysis process can lead to different H₂ color. Green hydrogen is obtained when the electrolyser is supplied only by renewable electricity and water. Renewable electricity includes PhotoVoltaic (PV), wind mainly. When the electricity comes from the grid, the hydrogen is called yellow hydrogen. Finally, a direct coupling of the electrolyser with nuclear results in pink hydrogen, the color category studied in NPHyCo project. It is more described in section 5.4.4.

All the pathways to produce hydrogen are characterized by different technical, economic and environmental parameters resulting in advantages and drawbacks for each technology. To be able to compare them, it is necessary to choose relevant Key Performance Indicators (KPIs).

5.2 Choose of relevant KPIs

The KPIs that can be used to present each retained hydrogen color belong to either technical category or economic category or environmental category. The selected indicators are summarized in Table 2.

Table 2: Summary of the techno-economic and environmental KPIs chosen for the comparison

Technical KPIs	Economic KPIs	Environmental KPIs
CRL (TRL) Size – H ₂ mass flow rate Purity of H ₂	LCOH	CO ₂ intensity Raw resources

The Commercial Readiness Level (CRL) or TRL gives the maturity of each technology.

The maximum available size or/and maximum available mass flow rates provide an idea of whether a single unit can meet a need or if multiple units are necessary, which would probably add some complexity.

The purity of hydrogen is an important indicator for industries. Depending on the industrial sector, the level of requirement varies. For example, the Osiris chemical platform has a requirement level of 99,995% to supply chemical industries. Purifiers can be added at the output of the production facility to reach the required level. Table 3 provides a detailed view of the different standards and the expected purity levels that are applied to hydrogen in China.

Table 3: Comparison of Hydrogen specification in National Standards for China [32]

Standard number	Name of standard	Grade	H2 purity (%)
GB/T 3634.1-2006	Hydrogen—Part 1: Industrial hydrogen	Qualified grade	>= 99
		First grade	>= 99,5
		Excellent grade	>= 99,95
GB/T 3634.2-2011	Hydrogen - Part 2: Pure hydrogen, high pure hydrogen and ultra-pure hydrogen	Pure hydrogen	>= 99,99
		High pure hydrogen	>= 99,999
		Ultrapure hydrogen	>= 99,9999
GB/T 16942-2009	Hydrogen for electronic industry	Grade I	>= 99,9999
		Grade II	>= 99,9997
		Grade III	>= 99,9995
GB/T 37244-2018	Fuel specification for proton exchange membrane fuel cell vehicles—Hydrogen	Hydrogen fuel for PEM FCVs	>= 99,97

Regarding economic indicators, one of the most used indicator is the LCOH. The LCOH is an indicator to be taken with caution because, on the one hand, it depends on the chosen scope and, on the other hand, it does not provide any indication of the controllability of the production means. This is more impactful with the Levelized Cost Of Electricity (LCOE), which does not reflect the non-controllability of renewable energies and thus the necessity of having backups at the national level. Some propose to replace the use of LCOE with Value-Added Levelized Cost of Electricity (VALCOE), which would better reflect the production means' capabilities to be flexible, to provide services to the grid, and to be available on demand [33].

Regarding environmental indicators, the most common one is the CO₂ intensity of hydrogen. However, it is also interesting to detail also the raw resources and in particular rare earth elements and/or noble metals.

5.3 Technical comparison

5.3.1 Grey hydrogen

There are four technologies for producing hydrogen from natural gas, three of them based on reforming [34]:

- Reforming:
 - Steam Methane Reforming (SMR): using water as an oxidant and a source of hydrogen.
 - Partial Oxidation (POX)⁵: using oxygen in the air as the oxidant.
 - Autothermal Reforming (ATR): a combination of SMR and POX
- Pyrolysis (PYR)

Coal gasification is also considered as grey hydrogen.

Table 4 gives an overview of the main advantages and drawbacks of the three common reforming process: SMR, POX and ATR.

Table 4: Summary of advantages and drawbacks of SMR, POX and ATR [42]

Technology	Advantages	Disadvantages
SMR	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • O₂ not required • Lowest temp. • Best H₂/CO ratio • High efficiency • Cost for large unit • Mostly used process 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Highest CO₂ emission • System is complex • System is sensitive to Natural Gas Qualities
POX	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • No catalyst required • Low methane slip • Simple system • Cost for small unit • Requires less desulphurization 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Low H₂/CO ratio • Very high temp • Soot formation/handling adds complexity • Pure O₂ requires
ATR	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Lower process temperature than POX • Low methane slip • Requires less O₂ than POX 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Limited commercial experience • Requires air or oxygen

5.3.1.1 SMR process

SMR process is used since 1930 at industrial scale in the United States [43]. The technology is very well known, the TRL is 9 and the technology is mature and available.

Figure 47 provides a schematic view of SMR process [44].

⁵ POX is mainly used to extract hydrogen from heavy fuel oil and coal

Figure 47: SMR process.

SMR is supplied by both electricity, water and generally natural gas or another gas containing hydrocarbons like ethane, propane, butane, pentane or light and heavy naphta.

The SMR process is composed of several sub steps. First, the natural gas or other methane containing hydrocarbons is sent to either a sulfur removal component or to a steam system. Two methods are typically used to remove the sulfur: chemical reactions such as the main commercial one which is HydroDeSulfurization (HDS) and adsorptive technology with activated carbon for instance. In a second step, the sulfur-free natural gas or other methane containing hydrocarbons and the steam enter into a reformer in which an endothermic reaction takes place at between 700°C and 1000°C:

At the output of the reformer, the syngas made of CO and H₂ is sent to WGSR. In this component, the following reaction takes place:

Then, CO₂ and other impurities are removed owing to Pressure-Swing Adsorption (PSA) process in order to get nearly pure hydrogen at the end. Excess water is sent to a treatment process and cooling towers and may be sent back to the steam system.

5.3.1.2 POX process

POX is a chemical reaction that occurs when a mixture of a hydrocarbon feedstock and a sub-stoichiometric amount of pure oxygen (O₂) are reacted together, producing a syngas stream with a typical H₂/CO ratio range of 1,6 to 1,8.

The hydrocarbon feedstock is fed into the POX reactor, where the carbon in the feedstock is reacted with oxygen in an exothermic reaction, forming carbon monoxide (CO). Since there is a lack of oxygen, the reaction does not complete to form carbon dioxide (CO₂).

In Figure 48, extracted from reference [38], is presented the POX process.

Figure 48: POX process.

Typically, all or a portion of the CO then flows to a water shift reactor, where the CO reacts with steam, forming a mixture of CO and H₂ (WGSR).

5.3.1.3 ATR process

ATR is an alternative technology in which the required heat is produced in the reformer itself. This means that all the CO₂ is produced inside the reactor. ATR uses both oxygen and water as oxidants, so it does not require or release heat, whether the steam and oxygen are in the right ratio.

The same reactions take place in the ATR process as in the SMR process. In Figure 49, extracted from reference [38], is presented the ATR process.

Figure 49: ATR process.

5.3.1.4 Coal gasification

Coal gasification is a process used since more than one hundred years. The technology is very well known, the TRL is 9 and the technology is mature and available.

In the literature, it is sometimes referred as brown hydrogen but in the most usual one, it is considered as grey hydrogen. This technology is largely used in China due to high prices of natural gas and large coal reserves. Different types of coal (lignite, sub-bituminous coal, bituminous coals and anthracites) are used as feedstock and different specific gasification methods can be used (fixed bed, moving bed, fluidized bed, entrained flow and plasma gasification). Nevertheless, all these processes need an operating temperature higher than 900°C. One of the main processes is depicted on Figure 50.

AL: N
ECCN: N

Figure 50: Coal gasification [31]

Dry coal is sent to the gasifier where it reacts with oxygen and steam under high temperature. The main outputs are CO₂ and H₂ obtained owing to two phases. First, the air is sent and oxidizes a fraction of the coal into CO₂. Then, air inflow is cut whereas steam is injected. The steam reacts with the coal to produce CO and H₂. Then, once the heat decreases to a particular point, air is once again sent to the gasifier and the two-phase process starts again. The global reaction in the gasifier is:

5.3.2 Blue hydrogen

In Europe most of the hydrogen is produced by SMR process and it is expected that ATR can become the technology of choice for new build hydrogen production facilities from natural gas. Carbon capture can be applied both to SMR and ATR hydrogen production, but ATR allows for the capture of emissions at lower cost than SMR because the CO₂ emissions are more concentrated.

In Figure 51, extracted from [46], is presented the carbon capture opportunities for SMR and ATR processes.

AL: N ECCN: N

Figure 51: Carbon capture opportunities for SMR and ATR processes.

As stated before, using SMR process up to around 40 % of the total emissions are concentrated in the flue gas. Using carbon capture with SMR plants can lead to a reduction in carbon emissions of up to 90 %, if applied to both process and flue gas streams. [46]

Because a higher proportion of the CO₂ produced is concentrated (a lower proportion is dilute flue gas CO₂) ATR is more amenable to the application of carbon capture. Overall, with ATR technology, decarbonization rates above 95 % can be reached. ATR may therefore become the preferred technology for new build hydrogen production facilities from natural where the aim is to achieve near-zero emissions production. [46]

According to European Industrial Gases Association (EIGA), there are three different options to capture CO₂.

Figure 52: Overview of the different options for carbon capture [47]

Option 1 is the Pre-combustion capture. In this option, the CO₂ is removed from the tail gas in the PSA unit owing to a CO₂ PSA or a cryogenic separation process. This option is relatively easy to setup on an existing process.

Option 2 is an alternative pre-combustion capture where the CO₂ is removed from the syngas directly after the shift reactor owing to a CO₂ PSA or a wash unit. This option is less energy intense than Option 1 but is retrofitting of an existing process is more complicated.

Option 3 is the Post-combustion capture. It is only for processes like SMR that require a combustion to generate the heat for the syngas reaction. It allows to capture CO₂ in the flue gas that are highly concentrated in CO₂. It can be set up on existing H₂ production plant, but investment and energy consumption are very high.

The use of one of these three options is really site-specific.

CCUS technology allows for the reduction of emissions from hydrogen-based products manufacturing (see Figure 53 extracted from [46]).

Figure 53: Carbon capture and usage or storage.

One of the main advantages of CCUS is that industrial facilities are able to carry out their process as usual by adding only a unit to capture CO₂. Another key benefit is that the cost of this CO₂ capture unit is relatively low, especially from gas streams where the CO₂ concentration is significantly high. Nevertheless, there is still the question of what to do with the CO₂ at the end as the potential for underground storage is limited.

Around the world, there are currently 26 Carbon Capture and Storage (CCS) plants in operation. Three of them are associated with hydrogen production, two of them for fertilizer production [46].

5.3.3 Green, pink, yellow hydrogen

These three pathways to produce hydrogen are based on electrolysis technology, the only difference is the electricity source: green hydrogen uses renewable energies as electricity source, yellow hydrogen uses the electrical network whereas pink hydrogen is obtained when nuclear energy is used as electricity source.

The most mature electrolysis technologies are Alkaline (AEL), Proton Exchange Membrane (PEM) for Low Temperature Electrolysis (LTE) and Solid Oxide Electrolysis Cell (SOEC) for High Temperature Steam Electrolysis (HTSE). These three technologies are already described in deliverable D1.1 [48] thus only summary of technical characteristics of each electrolysis technology is provided.

Table 5: Summary of the main technical characteristics of AEL, PEM and SOEC technologies [48] [49]

	AEL	PEM	SOEC
Operating temperature (°C)	60 - 80	50 - 80	700 - 1000
Operating pressure (bar)	30	30 - 80	1
Electrical efficiency (% LHV)	63 - 70	56 - 60	74 - 81
Stack degradation (%/1000h)	0,12	0,19	2
Stack lifetime (hours)	60000 - 90000	30000 - 90000	10000 - 30000
TRL (scale 1-9)	9	7-8	5-7
CRL	Mature and available	Mature and available (small scale)	Emerging
Biggest existing system (MWe)	150 Ningxia Solar Hydrogen Project (Phase 2)	20 Puertollano Green Hydrogen Plant (Spain) + Air Liquide's Bécancour Plant (Canada)	1 Hydrogen Lab Leuna (phase 1) (ongoing delivery of 2.6 MWe for MultiPHy project)
Coupling with NPP	Already existing: a 0,6-MWe HPP at Oskarshamn NPP in Sweden since 1992	Already existing: Nine Mile Point NPP in the US	Announced project: Prairie Island NPP in the US
Flexibility	Range of operation smaller than PEM Except for warm start-up, similar capabilities than PEM	Large range of operation Fast ramps Fast warm and cold start-up	Large range of operation Ramps and start-ups are slower than AEL
Purity	High-purity gas	High purity gas	Pure hydrogen
Space requirement (m ² /MWe)	100	50	150

5.3.4 Technical comparison

Table 6: Summary of the main technical characteristics of AEL, PEM, SOEC technologies and SMR, SMR+CCUS POX, ATR, Coal gasification processes [43]

	ALK	PEM	SOEC	SMR	POX	ATR	Coal gasification	SMR + CCUS
Operating temperature (°C)	60-80	50-80	700-1000	700-1000	> 1000	> 1000	700 - 1200	-
Operating pressure (bar)	1-30	30-80	1-20	15-50	40-100	30-100	25-100	-
TRL (scale 1-9)	9	7-8	5-7	9	9	9	9	9
CRL	Mature and available	Mature and available	Emerging	Mature and available	Mature and available	Early commercial	Mature and available	Mature and available
Biggest existing system	150 MWe Ningxia Solar Hydrogen Project (Phase 2)	20 MWe Puertollano Green Hydrogen Plant (Spain) + Air Liquide's Bécancour Plant (Canada)	1 MWe Hydrogen Lab Leuna (phase 1) (ongoing delivery of 2.6 MWe for MultiplHy project)	>= 1 ktons H2/day	NA	300 kNm ³ /h	NA	NA
Purity	High-purity gas	High purity gas	Pure hydrogen	High purity gas	High purity gas	High purity gas	High purity gas	-

ECCN: N

AL: N

5.4 Economical comparison

5.4.1 LCOH comparison between H₂ production routes

The European Hydrogen Observatory published in 2023 detailed LCOH per technology and Member States with 2022 data. The year 2022 is highly specific with high electricity and gas prices. As a result, calculated LCOH are higher than those for other years. Figure 54 **Erreur ! Source du renvoi introuvable.** presents the average LCOH by technology in Europe in 2022. Under their hypothesis, grey hydrogen is about 6 €/kg H₂, yellow hydrogen is about 9,85 €/kg H₂ and green hydrogen about 6,87 €/kg H₂. For comparison, with gas prices before 2020, grey hydrogen is commonly estimated at 2 €/kg H₂.

Figure 54: average levelized hydrogen production costs by technology in Europe in 2022 [34]

The literature provides a wide range of LCOH for different technologies provided by various sources, including agency reports, consultancy firms, and articles on techno-economic studies or online calculators that allow calculating LCOH with varying degrees of flexibility for changing assumptions.

However, interpreting LCOH cannot be separated from all the assumptions considered in the calculation, which is why it can be challenging to compare an LCOH value for a specific study with the literature. The importance of the country chosen for the study, which reflects different contexts ranging from renewable energy potential to energy prices (gas, electricity), incentives (specific contracts, different taxes), and Capital Expenditure (CAPEX) of production means, is significant in the final LCOH. The chosen scope is also crucial: the study may include compression, storage, and distribution or may stop right after production; thus, the hydrogen produced does not provide the same service. The size of the installation and the commissioning date are also two parameters that influence LCOH by changing the chosen CAPEX.

Figure 55 **Erreur ! Source du renvoi introuvable.** presents some LCOH found in the literature for different colors of hydrogen at different dates (2022, 2023 and 2030). It gathers data from IEA [1], Lazard [35], three university articles [36] [47] [48] and two online calculators [49] [50]. The color of a

bubble is linked to the color of hydrogen and its size is correlated to the size of the production plant. The name of the country considered in the study is also displayed.

Figure 55: Picture of LCOH found in the literature for three years (2022, 2023 and 2030), for different countries and for different colors of hydrogen [CEA]

More than the values, it is the trends and sensitivity to certain assumptions that are important to remember. This is why the exercise was done to illustrate this with calculations of LCOH for the different means of producing hydrogen, within a framework similar to what was done in deliverable D3.2.

The next sections present the Levelized Cost of Hydrogen for different producing routes: grey, blue, yellow, green with different electricity source: PV plant or onshore wind plant and pink hydrogen. For each section, economic data for LCOH computation and technical data for electrolyzers, SMR and carbon capture technologies come from IEA [1].

General assumptions are the following:

- Discount rate: 8%.
- Lifetime of the system: 25 years
- The same quantity of hydrogen is produced per year for all calculated LCOH: 4.198 t/year (as in D3.2 [30]).
- Gas and electricity prices are without taxes.

LCOH are calculated in output of the alkaline electrolyzer or of the SMR, without any storage or compression step. In fact, the LCOH is highly dependent on the hydrogen conditioning and transport. These two steps depend on the hydrogen use (mobility, iron production, ammonia, etc.).

5.4.2 Grey hydrogen - SMR process

As the hydrogen is still mainly produced by SMR, the costs associated to this technology can be considered as a reference and are very interesting for comparison with other hydrogen production technologies.

According to Hydrogen Europe [3], the LCOH by SMR really depends on the natural gas prices and on the CO₂ allowance. Thus, the recent increase in the natural gas price end of 2021 had a significant impact on the LCOH. More recently, in 2022, even more expensive natural gas prices were reached.

As a lot of SMR plants are already amortized, marginal costs may be a better benchmark for this technology instead of levelized costs.

The following figure presents the LCOH breakdown for hydrogen produced by SMR for different years that is for different gas prices. Average TTF gas prices in megawatt hours LHV for each year are taken and reminded in Table 7. This illustrates the impact of a gas prices increase like 2021 and 2022. The LCOH increased from 1,15 €/kg H₂ in 2019 to 2,76 €/kg H₂ in 2021 and reached 6,41 €/kg H₂ in 2022 without taking into account ETS (European Trading Scheme) tariff for CO₂. ETS tariff for CO₂ increased also since 2021 as reported in Table 7. Taking these later into account (hatched on the graph) leads to a LCOH increase from 1,45 €/kgH₂ in 2019 to 7,37 €/kg H₂ in 2022.

AL: N
ECCN: N

Figure 56: LCOH breakdown for SMR technologies.

Table 7: Average gas prices from 2019 to 2023 (Aleasoft database [51]), and ETS tariff for CO₂

	2019	2020	2021	2022	2023
TTF gas prices €/MWh HHV	13,55	9,34	46,50	123,47	40,68
TTF gas prices €/MWh LHV	15,06	10,38	51,67	137,19	45,20
ETS €/tCO ₂	25	25	50	80	80

5.4.3 Blue hydrogen – SMR + CCUS

Blue hydrogen is produced by SMR, but emitted CO₂ is captured and used or stored. According to [1], the capture unit add about 720 €/kW H₂ (LHV) before 2022 and 664 €/kW H₂ (LHV) after 2022 to the SMR CAPEX. The global process efficiency is lower than SMR alone: [1] estimates the SMR efficiency at 76% and SMR + CCUS at 69%. Additional cost is also needed to transport and store the carbon dioxide. IEA estimates this transport and storage costs at 51 €/t CO₂ [1] or 0,96 €/kg H₂.

The figure hereunder presents the LCOH breakdown for hydrogen produced by SMR + CCUS. LCOH of hydrogen produced by SMR with CCUS highly depend on gas prices. In 2022, the LCOH increased by a 3,6 factor compared to 2020, due to the increase of gas prices (10,38 €/MWh_{LHV} in 2020 and 138,19 €/MWh_{LHV} in 2022).

Figure 57: LCOH breakdown for SMR + CCUS from 2019 to 2023

5.4.4 Green, pink, yellow hydrogen

According to IEA [1], installed cost of electrolyzers has increased significantly since 2021 due to increasing cost of materials and labour. The next figure presents observed electrolyser prices for 2020, 2021 and 2022 and forecast for 2025 and 2030 [1] [52] [53]. The indicated range for each year corresponds to the alkaline technology (for the lowest) and PEM technology (for the highest). The year 2022 is highly specific with high investment costs increase.

Figure 58: Electrolyzer CAPEX from 2020 to 2022 and forecast.

5.4.4.1 Yellow hydrogen (electricity from grid)

Taking IEA's assumptions stated in the Global Hydrogen review and grid prices in Germany for 2020, 2021, 2022 and 2025, allows to calculate the LCOH for each year. Assumptions are the following:

- CAPEX : presented in Figure 58
- Operational Expenditure (OPEX): 3% of CAPEX [1]
- Efficiency of the electrolyser (LHV): 65% before 2022, 67% in 2025 [1]
- Grid prices (without taxes): extracted from Aleasoft database [51] (30,5 €/MWh in 2020, 96,9 €/kWh in 2021, 236,31€/kWh in 2022 and 95,23 €/kWh in 2023).
- The electrolyzer annual availability is 97% (as in D3.2 [30]).

The following figure presents the LCOH breakdown from 2020 to 2022 and the forecast for 2025. The CAPEX increase is significant with a 70% increase, but the electricity costs increase impacts much more the LCOH. Between 2020 and 2022 the LCOH has risen from 2,22 €/kg to 12,78 €/kg between 2020 and 2022. It is estimated that investment costs will decrease in 2025 [1].

Figure 59: LCOH Breakdown in Germany for electrolytic hydrogen supplied by the grid.

This analysis highlights the impact of the grid electricity prices on the LCOH.

5.4.4.2 Green hydrogen with PV

Assumptions for electrolyser are the same (1000 USD/MW in 2020, OPEX set at 3% CAPEX, efficiency of 65%). The PV load factor in Europe is between 10% in Finland and 17% in Spain (12% in Germany and 14% in France) [44]. These load factors correspond to 876 full load hours equivalent and 1489 full load hours equivalent. The LCOE of solar PV is extracted from [16] and is about 49 USD/MWh (45,8 €/MWh). The following graphic presents the LCOH under selected assumptions for different load factor. The first bar (load factor of 12%) represents the case in Germany for a PV plant size equal to the electrolyzer size. The LCOH is then about 7,7 €/kg H₂. The second one represents the case in France (load factor of 14%) and the third one the case in Spain (17%), with respectively a LCOH of 6,9 €/kg H₂ and 6,1 €/kg H₂. The other bars are for cases where the PV plant size is higher than the electrolyser size (the last bar is for a PV plant 3.8 times higher than the electrolyzer size). In this graph, no electricity or hydrogen storages are considered. It could represent a situation with a one-month temporal correlation between solar electricity generation and use by electrolyzer as stated in the RED II delegated act (see 4.1.2.1). Higher is the load factor, lower is the LCOH.

Figure 60 - LCOH breakdown according to PV load factor.

N
ECCN: With a PV sourcing, the global business model has to be studied with, among others, the following questions: can the electricity not used by the electrolyser be sold and at what price? Could an electricity storage be profitable allowing a better load factor for the electrolyser? If the final hydrogen demand is stable, what would be the size of the needed hydrogen storage?

N
AL: The intermittency of PV is highly challenging for a hydrogen production.

5.4.4.3 Green hydrogen with wind

Assumptions for electrolyser are the same (1000 USD/MW in 2020, OPEX set at 3% CAPEX, efficiency of 65%). The wind load factor in Europe is between 20% in average in Germany and 26% in average [16]. These load factors correspond to 1752 full load hours equivalent and 2277 full load hours equivalent. The LCOE of wind onshore is extracted from [16] and is about 33 USD/MWh (30,8 €/MWh). The following graphic presents the LCOH under selected assumptions for different load factors. The first bar (load factor of 20%) represents the case in Germany for a wind plant size equal to the electrolyzer size. The LCOH is then about 4,77 €/kg H₂. The third one represents the case in Spain (26%), with a LCOH of 4,04 €/kg H₂. The other bars are for cases where the wind plant size is higher than the electrolyzer size (1.5 times for the last bar). In this graph, no electricity or hydrogen storages are considered. It could represent a situation with a one-month temporal correlation between solar electricity generation and use by electrolyser as stated in the RED II delegated act (see 4.1.2.1). Higher is the load factor, lower is the LCOH.

Figure 61: LCOH breakdown according to wind load factor.

Compared to PV, load factors are higher (more than 1,5 times higher) and LCOE is lower (-32%). That allows to obtain better LCOH with wind than with PV, even if PV generation is more predictable. Nevertheless, the same questions are raised for wind electricity sourcing: can the electricity not used by the electrolyser be sold and at what price? Could an electricity storage be profitable allowing a better load factor for the electrolyser? If the final hydrogen demand is stable, what would be the size of the needed hydrogen storage?

5.4.4.4 Pink hydrogen

Assumptions for electrolyzer are the same (1000 USD/MW in 2020, OPEX set at 3% CAPEX, efficiency of 65%). The LCOE of nuclear is extracted from D3.1 for NPP at 85% capacity factor, new build and with Long Term Operation (LTO) of 20 years and for a WACC of 7% (Table 8).

Table 8: Projected costs of generating electricity 2020 - IEA and NEA, for NPP at 85% capacity factor and WACC of 7%, new build and with LTO of 20 years

Country	NPP new build (€/MWh)	NPP with LTO 20 years (€/MWh)
France	71,1	30,65
Japan	86,67	-
Korea	53,3	-
Russia	42,02	-
Slovak Republic	101,84	-
United States	71,25	-
Sweden	-	28,17

Erreur ! Source du renvoi introuvable.

Deliverable 3.3, Revision A

The following figure presents the LCOH breakdown for different LCOE of nuclear electricity. The lowest LCOH (2,1 and 2,2 €/kg H₂) are obtained for NPP with LTO of 20 years and corresponding LCOE of respectively 26,4 and 28,6 €/MWh. The advantages of a direct connection of the HPP to a NPP are to have high load factors and stable prices over the years, reducing the risks for the hydrogen producer.

Figure 62: LCOH breakdown for different LCOE of nuclear electricity

5.4.5 Economic comparison

For this comparison, the following assumptions are taken (already stated in 0):

- Discount rate: 8%
- Lifetime of the system: 25 years
- The same quantity of hydrogen is produced per year for all calculated LCOH: 4 198 t/year (as in D3.2 for continuous operation strategy).
- LCOH are calculated in output of the alkaline electrolyzer or of the SMR, without any storage or compression step.
- CAPEX, OPEX and efficiency presented in 5.4.4.

The following figure presents the LCOH comparison for different hydrogen production technologies in 2023. The most favourable European country has been chosen. The lowest LCOH (2,00 €/kg) is obtained with nuclear with LTO in France. In Sweden, electricity prices were low in 2024 (about 40 €/MWh). Consequently, with electricity from the grid, the LCOH is about 2,50 €/kg H₂. These electricity prices seem to be an exception in Europe thus this case can not be used as a reference. The same year French grid prices were higher (about 97 €/MWh) and that leads to the highest LCOH of the comparison (5,33 €/kg H₂). Hydrogen produced with wind, new built nuclear, SMR or SMR + CCUS present quite similar LCOH with respectively 3,43 €/kg H₂, 3,88 €/kg H₂, 3,34 €/kg H₂ and 3,86 €/kg H₂. Hydrogen produced with solar electricity presents higher LCOH (5,17 €/kg) due to the low capacity factor of PV.

Figure 63: LCOH comparison for different hydrogen production technologies, 2023.

The low-capacity factor of PV and to a lesser extent of wind impacts the electrolyser capacity needed to produce a given yearly amount of hydrogen. The table hereunder present the calculated electrolyser capacity needed for each electricity sourcing and the associated load factor. An efficiency of 67% is considered [1] for 2025. With a solar electricity sourcing, the required electrolyser size is 5,7 times higher than with the grid. This is why the electrolyser’s CAPEX share is higher for PV sourcing than for grid or nuclear (Figure 63).

Table 9: Capacity factor and corresponding electrolyzer size according to electricity sourcing [1] [16]

Electricity sourcing	Grid	PV	Wind	Nuclear
Capacity factor	97%	17%	26%	85%
Electrolyzer size (MW)	24,6	140,2	91,7	28,0
Annual H2 production (kt)	4 198			

Although, PV, Wind or nuclear sourcing have lower capacity factors and consequently higher electrolyser sizes, they allow to reduce the investment risk if long term contracts can be contracted. In comparison, electricity and gas grid prices are subject to high variability.

The best trade-off between load factor, LCOE and low carbon hydrogen is obtained with nuclear LTO.

5.5 Environmental aspects

5.5.1 Grey and blue hydrogen - SMR process

According to IEA [1], direct emissions of hydrogen produced by SMR are around 9 kg CO_{2 eq}/kg H₂. Indirect emissions occur during the production, the processing and transport of natural gas: methane venting, leakages or energy used. They are estimated at 2,4 kg CO_{2 eq}/kg H₂. The global carbon emissions of hydrogen produced by SMR without CCUS is then about 10 – 13 kg CO_{2 eq}/kg H₂.

With a 93% capture rate, CCUS allow to reduce direct emissions to 0,7 kg CO_{2 eq}/kg H₂. The total emissions range between 1,5 and 6,2 kg CO_{2 eq}/kg H₂.

Nevertheless, methane leaks during transportation and production natural gas are often underestimated and the storage of CO₂ captured owing to CCUS is also a problem that will be raised [31].

5.5.2 Green, pink, yellow hydrogen

Carbon content of electrolytic hydrogen depend on the electricity sourcing (renewable, nuclear or electricity of the grid). The following figure, extracted from [3] presents the carbon intensity of hydrogen produced from grid electricity. Hydrogen carbon intensity is highly dependent on the carbon grid content. In Island, Sweden, Norway, Luxembourg and France, hydrogen produced from grid electricity can be considered as low carbon. In half of European countries, carbon intensity of hydrogen produced from grid is higher than grey hydrogen. Consequently, a particular attention must be paid to the carbon content of the grid for yellow hydrogen.

ECCN: N
AL: N

Figure 64: Carbon intensity of hydrogen produced from grid electricity [3]

Erreur ! Source du renvoi introuvable.

Deliverable 3.3, Revision A

According to Ademe [54], the carbon content of hydrogen produced with PV is about 2,58 kg CO₂eq/kg H₂ in France and for hydrogen produced with wind it is about 0,7 kg CO₂ eq/kg H₂. According to IEA [1], nuclear hydrogen has an emission intensity in the range of 0.1 – 0.3 kg CO₂ eq/kg H₂.

Depending on the electrolyser technology, different raw resources are used. The alkaline electrolyzer uses aluminum, copper, graphite, nickel, and zirconium. The electrolyte, often KOH, is a hazardous product that leads to an environmental risk. PEM electrolyzer requires noble metals such as platinum, in addition to aluminum and copper. Regarding the SOEC, it uses rare earth elements such as lanthanum or yttrium in addition to other raw resources.

5.5.3 Environmental comparison

The following figure, extracted from [1], presents the comparison of the emissions intensity of different hydrogen production technologies. The main production route is currently natural gas without CCS. It has an emissions intensity of 10 to 13 kg CO₂ eq/kg H₂. Coupling SMR with CCS 93% allows to cut off emissions by 48% to 88% compared to SMR without CCS. Coal gasification has a higher emission intensity with 22 to 26 kg CO₂ eq/kg H₂. Solar, wind and nuclear hydrogen have a carbon content less than 3 kg CO₂ eq/kg H₂

Figure 65: Comparison of the emissions intensity of different hydrogen production [1]

6 Conclusion

Hydrogen consumption in Europe was about 8,2 Mt in 2022. Germany, the Netherlands, Poland and Spain was responsible for more than half of this hydrogen consumption. The main hydrogen uses are currently refining and ammonia production. Traditional hydrogen production by methane reforming represents 91% of European production capacity. At the end of 2022, 174 MW of electrolyzer capacity were in operation in Europe, producing about 30 000 tons of hydrogen annually and representing 0,3 % of the overall total hydrogen production capacity.

The future green hydrogen demand can be estimated between 5,7 and 6,4 Mt in 2035. The two main uses would be SAF and the steel industry with respectively 2,2 Mt. Other main uses would be transports, shipping, ammonia production, methanol production and refining. These accounting estimates are only indicative as forecasts are subject to considerable uncertainty. Most important traditional hydrogen uses are requiring average unit sizes over 100 MW (ammonia, refining, methanol, steel). In the context of the NPHyCo project, with a 45 MW electrolyzer, only smaller applications should be targeted such as other chemicals or new uses such as transport or SAF. Regarding the road transportation, the average size of refueling station should be around 1 to 2 tons of hydrogen per day, that is an equivalent electrolyzer capacity of 2 to 4 MW. Nevertheless, the hydrogen production can be located on-site with small electrolyzer (2 – 4 MW) or centralized with bigger electrolyzer, from 20 to 100 MW. In the case of centralization, hydrogen have to be transported with tube trailers or pipelines.

Expected volumes of renewable hydrogen produced in Europe by 2035 are very important (6 Mt according to section 3.1, more than 10 Mt according to RePowerEU targets). This deployment will face several challenges. The regulatory framework is quite new and is evolving rapidly. A changing regulatory framework can hinder the hydrogen deployment because of uncertain environment for investors. Electricity needs to feed electrolyzer are huge (480 TWh/year for 10 Mt/year of hydrogen) and new renewable plants and grid reinforcement will be needed to ensure a renewable hydrogen production. This will lead to a need for massive hydrogen storage in order to deal with intermittency and seasonality of renewable energies. Finally, to transport hydrogen from massive storages to consumption sites, a hydrogen infrastructure have to be developed to ensure a harmonized deployment of renewable hydrogen.

The economical comparison showed that the lowest LCOH is obtained with nuclear with long term operation. Carbon content and LCOH of yellow hydrogen (with grid electricity) is highly dependent on grid prices and carbon content of the grid. In some country both criteria (LCOH and carbon content) are meet with a low carbon hydrogen and a low LCOH but in other the carbon content is higher than grey hydrogen and LCOH not competitive. Hydrogen produced with wind, new built nuclear, SMR or SMR + CCUS present quite similar LCOH. Hydrogen produced with solar electricity presents higher LCOH due to the low capacity factor of PV. Although, PV, Wind or nuclear sourcing have lower capacity factors and consequently higher electrolyzer sizes, they allow to reduce the investment risk if long term contracts can be contracted. In comparison, electricity and gas grid prices are subject to high variability. The best trade-off between load factor, LCOE and low carbon hydrogen is obtained with nuclear LTO. It is important to note that LCOH are highly dependent on countries boundary conditions (solar and wind resources, grid prices and carbon intensity).

N
ECCN:
N
AL:

7 Bibliography

- [1] IEA, «Global Hydrogen Review 2023,» 2023.
- [2] European Hydrogen Observatory, “Datasets,” [Online]. Available: <https://observatory.clean-hydrogen.europa.eu/tools-reports/datasets>.
- [3] Hydrogen Europe, «Clean hydrogen monitor,» 2023.
- [4] Linde, “Refining Expectations - with Gases and Equipment from Linde,” [Online]. Available: <https://www.linde-gas.com/industries/refining>.
- [5] IRENA, «Innovation Outlook Renewable Ammonia,» 2022.
- [6] F. Europe, «Forecast of food, farming and fertilizer use in the EU 2021-2031».
- [7] European Commission, «2020 Annual Report on CO2 Emissions from Maritime Transport,» 2021.
- [8] IRENA, «A pathway to decarbonise the shipping sector by 2050,» Abu Dhabi, 2021.
- [9] Eurofer, “Overview of the steelmaking process,” [Online]. Available: <https://www.eurofer.eu/about-steel/learn-about-steel/what-is-steel-and-how-is-steel-made>.
- [10] C. Yilmaz, J. Wendelstorf and T. Turek, “Modeling and simulation of hydrogen injection into a blast furnace to reduce carbon dioxide emissions,” *Journal of Cleaner Production*, vol. 154, pp. 488-501, 2017.
- [11] European Commission, «A Clean Planet for all,» 2018.
- [12] European Parliamentary Research Service, «The potential of hydrogen for decarbonising EU industry,» 2021.
- [13] Agora Energiewende, «No-regret hydrogen: Charting early steps for H2 infrastructure in Europe,» 2021.
- [14] Eurofer, «Map of EU steel production sites».
- [15] Methanol Institute, “Applications,” [Online]. Available: <https://www.methanol.org/applications/>.
- [16] IRENA, «Renewable Power Generation,» 2022.
- [17] Hydrogen Europe website, “A new dawn for H2 mobility in EU,” 2023. [Online]. Available: <https://hydrogeneurope.eu/a-new-dawn-for-h2-mobility-in-eu/>.
- [18] Eurostat, “Net electricity generation by type of fuel - monthly data,” [Online]. Available: https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/databrowser/view/NRG_CB_PEM__custom_5180368/default/table?lang=en.
- [19] EU Aviation Safety Agency (EASA), «European Aviation Environmental Report 2022,» 2022.

- [20] IRENA, «Green Hydrogen for Industry,» 2022.
- [21] European Commission, «A hydrogen strategy for a climate-neutral Europe,» 2020.
- [22] European Commission, «The European Hydrogen Bank,» 2023.
- [23] D. Zivar, S. Kumar and J. Foroozesh, “Underground hydrogen storage: A comprehensive review,” *International Journal of Hydrogen Energy*, vol. 46, no. 45, pp. 23436-23462, 2021.
- [24] D. G. Caglayan, N. Weber, H. U. Heinrichs, J. Linßen, M. Robinius, P. A. Kukla and D. Stolten, “Technical potential of salt caverns for hydrogen storage in Europe,” *International Journal of Hydrogen Energy*, vol. 45, no. 11, pp. 6793-6805, 2020.
- [25] R. Ahluwalia, D. Papadimas, J.-K. Peng and H. Roh, “System Level Analysis of Hydrogen Storage Options,” 2019.
- [26] Clean Hydrogen Joint Undertaking, «Strategic Research and Innovation Agenda 2021-2027,» 2022.
- [27] JRC, «Assessment of Hydrogen Delivery Options,» 2022.
- [28] ENTSOG, «Entsog 2050 Roadmap for Gas Grids,» 2024.
- [29] European Hydrogen Backbone (EHB), «European hydrogen infrastructure vision covering 28 countries,» 2022.
- [30] C. Herrero, S. Crevon, P. Lukasova, G. Laviaille, J. C. Marti et J. A. Ruiz, «D3.2 Techno-economic incomes models for NPHYCO Business Plan. Operational strategies for nuclear powered hydrogen,» 2024.
- [31] A. Ajanovic, M. Sayer and R. Haas, “The economics and the environmental benignity of different colors of hydrogen,” *International Journal of Hydrogen Energy*, vol. 47, no. 57, pp. 24136-24154, 2022.
- [32] Y. Yang, G. Wang, L. Zhang, S. Zhang and L. Lin, “Comparison of Hydrogen Specification in National Standards for China,” *2019 4th International Conference on Advances in Energy and Environment Research (ICAEEER 2019)*, 2019.
- [33] IEA, «Global Energy and Climate Model Documentation - 2023,» 2023.
- [34] P. J. Megia, A. J. Vizcaino, J. A. Calles and A. Carrero, “Hydrogen Production Technologies: From Fossil Fuels toward Renewable Sources. A mini review,” *Energy & Fuels*, vol. 35, no. 20, 2021.
- [35] R. Chaubey, S. Sahu, O. O. James and S. Maity, “A review on development of industrial processes and emerging techniques for production of hydrogen from renewable and sustainable sources,” *Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews*, vol. 23, pp. 443-462, 2013.
- [36] Technique de l'Ingénieur, «Production des gaz de synthèse par vaporeformage,» 2022.
- [37] R. Pinsky, P. Sabharwall, J. Hartvigsen and J. O. Brien, “Comparative review of hydrogen production technologies for nuclear hybrid energy systems,” *Progress in Nuclear Energy*, vol. 123, 2020.

- [38] Global Syngas Technologies Council (GSTC), "Syngas Technology," [Online]. Available: <https://globalsyngas.org/about/>.
- [39] Hydrogen Europe, «Clean ammonia in the future energy system,» 2023.
- [40] EIGA, «Overview of hydrogen production methods».
- [41] CVR, Hunatom, Framatome, Nucleareurope, Ansaldo, Tecnatom, «Project Frame of Reference,» 2023.
- [42] NPHYCO, «Impact Assessment Report,» 2024.
- [43] IEA, "CCUS Technology Innovation," [Online]. Available: <https://www.iea.org/reports/ccus-in-clean-energy-transitions/ccus-technology-innovation>.
- [44] European Hydrogen Observatory, «The European hydrogen market landscape,» 2023.
- [45] Lazard, «LCOE+,» 2023.
- [46] R. D. Lopez, J. M. Lujano-Rojas and J. L. Bernal-Agustin, "Optimisation of size and control strategy in utility-scale green hydrogen production systems," *International Journal of Hydrogen Energy*, vol. 50, pp. 292-309, 2024.
- [47] L. Povacz and R. Bhandari, "Analysis of the Levelized Cost of Renewable Hydrogen in Austria," *Sustainability*, 2023.
- [48] T. Lundblad, M. Taljegard and F. Johnsson, "Centralized and decentralized electrolysis-based hydrogen supply systems for road transportation – A modeling study of current and future costs," *International Journal of Hydrogen Energy*, vol. 48, no. 12, pp. 4830-4844, 2023.
- [49] Agora Energiewende, "Levelised Cost of Hydrogen Calculator," [Online]. Available: <https://www.agora-energiewende.org/data-tools/levelised-cost-of-hydrogen-calculator>.
- [50] Hydrogen European Observatory, "Levelised Cost Of Hydrogen Calculator," [Online]. Available: <https://observatory.clean-hydrogen.europa.eu/tools-reports/levelised-cost-hydrogen-calculator>.
- [51] AleaSoft, "Database," [Online]. Available: <https://app.aleasoft.com/login>.
- [52] IEA, «Global Hydrogen Review 2022,» 2022.
- [53] IEA, «Global Hydrogen Review 2021,» 2021.
- [54] ADEME, "Base GES," [Online]. Available: <https://base-empreinte.ademe.fr/donnees/jeu-donnees>.
- [55] A. Tripodi, F. Conte and I. Rossetti, "Carbon Dioxide Methanation: Design of a Fully Integrated Plant," *Energy Fuels*, vol. 34, no. 6, pp. 7242-7256, 2020.
- [56] L. Dehdari, I. Burgers, P. Xiao, K. G. Li, R. Singh and P. A. Webley, "Purification of hydrogen from natural gas/hydrogen pipeline mixtures," *Separation and Purification Technology*, vol. 282, 2022.

- [57] European Hydrogen Backbone (EHB), «Implementation roadmap - cross border projects and cost update,» 2023.
- [58] Y. Manoharan, S. E. Hosseini, B. Butler, H. Alzahrani, B. T. F. Senior, T. Ashuri and J. Krohn, “Hydrogen Fuel Cell Vehicles; Current Status and Future Prospect,” *Applied Science*, 2019.
- [59] IRENA, «Innovation Outlook Renewable Methanol,» 2021.
- [60] Methanol Institute, «Ship Energy Survey 2024,» 2024.
- [61] S. Lu, Y. Shi, N. Meng, S. Lu, Y. Yu and B. Zhang, “Electrosynthesis of Syngas via the Co-Reduction of CO₂ and H₂O,” *Cell Reports Physical Science*, vol. 1, no. 11, 2020.
- [62] J. Lin, Y. Zhang, P. Xu and L. Chen, “CO₂ electrolysis: Advances and challenges in electrocatalyst engineering and reactor design,” *Materials Reports: Energy*, vol. 3, no. 2, 2023.
- [63] J. Herranz, A. Patru, E. Fabbri and T. J. Schmidt, “Co-electrolysis of CO₂ and H₂O: From electrode reactions to cell-level development,” *Current Opinion in Electrochemistry*, vol. 23, pp. 89-95, 2020.
- [64] D. Dogu, S. Gunduz and K. Meyer, “CO₂ and H₂O Electrolysis Using Solid Oxide Electrolyzer Cell (SOEC) with La and Cl-doped Strontium Titanate Cathode,” *Catal Lett*, vol. 149, pp. 1743-1752, 2019.
- [65] IRENA, «Global hydrogen trade to meet the 1.5°C climate goal,» 2022.
- [66] IRENA, «Reaching zero with renewables,» 2020.
- [67] IEA, «The future of hydrogen. Seizing today's opportunities,» 2019.
- [68] Concawe, «A look into the role of e-fuels in the transport system in Europe (2030-2050),» 2019.
- [69] Agora Energiewende, «The future cost of electricity-based synthetic fuels,» 2018.
- [70] ElementEnergy, «Hydrogen Use in Aviation - Transport and Environment,» 2022.
- [71] EPRS, «EU rules for renewable hydrogen,» 2023.
- [72] SyngasChem, “Synthesis Gas Chemistry and Synthetic Fuels,” [Online]. Available: <https://www.syngaschem.com/syngas/>.
- [73] Karlsruhe Institute of Technology - IMVT, “Power-to-methanol: Experimental and modeling work for CO₂ capture and its application in combination with methanol synthesis,” [Online]. Available: https://www.imvt.kit.edu/english/57_1931.php.
- [74] Dynamic Equilibrium, “What is the methanol production process,” [Online]. Available: <https://everythingdynamicequilibrium.weebly.com/methanol-production.html>.
- [75] NaturPhilosophie, “Nitrogen - Nature's explosive building blocks,” [Online]. Available: <https://www.naturphilosophie.co.uk/nitrogen-natures-explosive-building-blocks/>.
- [76] LibreTexts Chemistry, “The Haber-Bosch Reaction Can Be Surface Catalyzed,” [Online]. Available: https://chem.libretexts.org/Bookshelves/Physical_and_Theoretical_Chemistry_Textbook_Maps/P

hysical_Chemistry_(LibreTexts)/31%3A_Solids_and_Surface_Chemistry/31.10%3A_The_Haber-Bosch_Reaction_Can_Be_Surface_Catalyzed.

- [77] S. Geleynse, K. Brandt, M. Garcia-Perez and X. Z. Michael Wolcott, "The Alcohol-to-Jet Conversion Pathway for Drop-In Biofuels: Techno-Economic Evaluation," *ChemSusChem*, vol. 11, no. 21, pp. 3728-3741, 2018.
- [78] G. Pipitone, G. Zoppi, R. Pirone and S. Bensaid, "Sustainable aviation fuel production using in-situ hydrogen supply via aqueous phase reforming: A techno-economic and life-cycle greenhouse gas emissions assessment," *Journal of Cleaner Production*, vol. 418, 2023.
- [79] L. Zeng, M. Sarmadivaleh, A. Saeedi, Y. Chen, Z. Zhong and Q. Xie, "Storage integrity during underground hydrogen storage in depleted gas reservoirs," *Earth-Science Review*, vol. 247, 2023.
- [80] S. Sollai, A. Porcu, V. Tola and F. Ferrara, "Renewable methanol production from green hydrogen and captured CO₂: A techno-economic assessment," *Journal of CO₂ utilization*, 2023.

ECCN: N

AL: N

8 Annexes

8.1 Annex 1 – European consumption and production, full tables

Table 10: European hydrogen consumption by country in 2022 (t/yr) [2]

Country	Clean consumption (t/yr)	Other consumption (t/yr)	Total consumption (t/yr)
Austria	815	115300	116115
Belgium	180	377985	378165
Bulgaria	0	121192	121192
Croatia	0	62336	62336
Czechia	0	104110	104110
Denmark	534	24756	25289
Estonia	17	0	17
Finland	1090	175267	176357
France	669	549080	549748
Germany	7447	1729162	1736609
Greece	112	326423	326536
Hungary	0	187872	187872
Iceland	753	0	753
Ireland	0	8227	8227
Italy	303	607439	607742
Latvia	0	67	67
Lithuania	0	143687	143687
Luxemburg	0	575	575
Netherlands	483	983560	984043
Norway	922	155791	156713
Poland	0	784020	784020
Portugal	0	103346	103346
Romania	0	133780	133780
Slovakia	0	105386	105386
Slovenia	0	1809	1809
Spain	2810	609022	611831
Sweden	1135	173556	174692
Switzerland	1557	18993	20550
UK	762	568226	568988

AL: N
ECCN: N

Country	Clean consumption (t/yr)	Other consumption (t/yr)	Total consumption (t/yr)
TOTAL	19588	8170967	8190555

Table 11: European hydrogen consumption by end-use in 2022 (t/yr) [3]

End-use	Application	Clean consumption (t/yr)	Other consumption (t/yr)	Total consumption (t/yr)
Refining	Traditional	1821	4629445	4631266
Ammonia		2248	2004167	2006415
Methanol		674	242806	243481
Other chemicals		1343	710296	711639
Other		5409	307929	313338
Industrial heat	Emerging	0	276025	276025
Mobility		3211	300	3511
Steel		1542	0	1542
Blending in NG		1922	0	1922
E-fuels		1101	0	1101
Residential heat		225	0	225
Power generation		92	0	92
TOTAL		19588	8170967	8190555

AL: N
ECCN: N

Table 12: European hydrogen consumption by country and end-use in 2022 (t/yr) [3]

Country	Refining (t/yr)	Ammonia (t/yr)	Industrial Heat (t/yr)	Methanol (t/yr)	Other Chemicals (t/yr)	Others (t/yr)	Total (t/yr)
Austria	36107	70924	3600		4026	1458	116115
Belgium	168253	136094	31061		42540	217	378165
Bulgaria	69281	48605	3287			19	121192
Croatia	52596	9721				19	62336
Czechia	46505	37286	4788		15288	243	104110
Denmark	24363			56		871	25289
Estonia					17	0	17
Finland	142017		3925		29404	1011	176357
France	310937	151706	36870		26718	23518	549748
Germany	872869	358116	69483	150993	98960	186187	1736609
Greece	304866	21386	164			120	326536
Hungary	55322	59514	5288		66240	1507	187872
Iceland				674		79	753
Ireland	7652				213	362	8227
Italy	500844	77768	10686		11267	7177	607742
Latvia						67	67
Lithuania	47168	96519				0	143687
Luxemburg						575	575
Netherlands	396665	261473	40053	20743	224705	40404	984043
Norway	37015	64807	9489	42429	2004	970	156713
Poland	380999	374372	8937		13846	5866	784020
Portugal	87600		6142		9592	12	103346
Romania	71260	44976	3317	14196		31	133780
Slovakia	92975	8469	2041		1590	311	105386
Slovenia			263		1537	9	1809
Spain	478901	66299	14519		17719	34393	611831
Sweden	125821		9014	14390	23802	1664	174692
Switzerland	12335				6977	1238	20550
UK	308915	118380	13097		115194	13402	568988
TOTAL	4631266	2006415	276025	243481	711639	321729	8190555

AL: N
ECCN: N

Table 13: European clean hydrogen consumption by country and end-use in 2022 (t/year) [2]

Country	Refining (t/yr)	Ammonia (t/yr)	Methanol (t/yr)	Other Chemicals (t/yr)	Other (t/yr)	Emerging applications (t/yr)	Total (t/yr)
Austria					111	704	815
Belgium					142	37	180
Denmark					476	57	534
Estonia				17			17
Finland	79				1012		1090
France					163	506	669
Germany	1742			539	1039	4126	7447
Greece					112		112
Iceland			674		75	3	753
Italy					219	85	303
Netherlands						483	483
Norway					843	79	922
Spain		2248			523	39	2810
Sweden					610	526	1135
Switzerland				787	7	762	1557
UK					77	685	762
TOTAL	1821	2248	674	1343	5409	8092	19588

AL: N
ECCN: N

Table 14: European hydrogen production capacity by country in 2022 (t/yr) [2]

Country	Production capacity (t/yr)	Production capacity (MW _{el})	Output (t/yr)	Production utilization by capacity (%)
Austria	171 577	7	115472	67
Belgium	523 308	2	411230	79
Bulgaria	181 703	0	121173	67
Croatia	149 899	0	62317	42
Czechia	132 557	0	103866	78
Denmark	31 361	5	24953	40
Estonia	26	0	0	68
Finland	199 123	10	176436	89
France	822 712	6	552823	67
Germany	2 148 948	66	1743512	81
Greece	359 741	1	326557	91
Hungary	257 620	0	188005	73
Iceland	1 107	7	753	68
Ireland	9 873	0	7864	80
Italy	829240	3	607913	73
Lithuania	266934	0	143687	54
Netherlands	1424259	4	975234	68
Norway	287882	8	157610	55
Poland	1104772	0	784637	71
Portugal	110876	0	106285	96
Romania	247355	0	134335	54
Slovakia	221860	0	105598	48
Slovenia	2419	0	1847	76
Spain	797029	25	614471	77
Sweden	242346	10	175367	72
Switzerland	24728	14	20550	83
UK	783674	7	569135	73
TOTAL	11332929	174	8231646	73

AL: N
ECCN: N

Table 15: European hydrogen production capacity by process type and end-use in 2022 (t/yr) [2]

Process	Subprocess	End-use	Production capacity (t/yr)	Production capacity (MW _{el})	Output (t/yr)
Reforming	N/A	Refining	5350242		4479856
		Ammonia	3539160		2037199
		Methanol	506938		242806
		Other chemicals	668588		523268
		Unknown	246059		191926
Reforming	Carbon capture	Refining	13394		9728
		Other industry	4746		4319
		Unknown	1182		922
By-product	Ethylene Styrene	Refining	341307		267707
	Ethylene Styrene Chlor-alkali Sodium chlorate	Other chemicals	347327		257740
	Styrene	Industrial heat	9889		5790
	Chlor-alkali Sodium chlorate	Unknown	275292		190796
	Water electrolysis	N/A	Ammonia	3306	20
Refining			2678	16,2	1821
Blending in NG			2826	17,1	1922
E-fuels			1620	9,8	1101
Methanol			992	6	674
Mobility			8994	54,4	6116
Other chemicals			1975	12	1343
Power generation			135	0,8	92
Residential heat			331	2	225
Steel			2268	13,7	1542
Unknown			3683	22	2504
TOTAL			11332929	174	8231646

ECCN: N

AL: N

Table 16: European hydrogen production capacity by country and process type in 2022 (t/year) [2]

Country	Reforming (t/yr)	Reforming CC (t/yr)	By-product (t/yr)	Water electrolysis (t/yr)	Total (t/yr)
Austria	158030		12349	1198	171577
Belgium	444821		78222	264	523308
Bulgaria	174016		7686		181703
Croatia	149899				149899
Czechia	118648		13909		132557
Denmark	30576			785	31361
Estonia				26	26
Finland	174266		23254	1603	199123
France	700517	13394	107817	983	822712
Germany	1847833		290164	10951	2148948
Greece	359296		280	165	359741
Hungary	232907		24713		257620
Iceland				1107	1107
Ireland	9565		308		9873
Italy	785023	1182	42589	446	829240
Lithuania	266934				266934
Netherlands	1258168	4746	160634	711	1424259
Norway	266030		20497	1355	287882
Poland	1081622		23150		1104772
Portugal	98950		11926		110876
Romania	241699		5656		247355
Slovakia	216062		5799		221860
Slovenia	1971		448		2419
Spain	744684		48212	4132	797029
Sweden	197794		42882	1669	242346
Switzerland	21123		1316	2289	24728
UK	730551		52003	1120	783674
TOTAL	10310985	19322	973815	28808	11332929

AL: N ECCN: N

8.2 Annex 2 – Methanation and separation

8.2.1 Methanation

Methanation, which consists of the conversion of carbon oxides into methane through hydrogenation, is a means of obtaining synthetic natural gas.

Methanation process, which is based on the Sabatier reaction, can be divided into two steps [55]:

The efficient direct conversion of CO₂ and H₂ into CH₄ relies on the actual selectivity of the catalysts (based mainly on Ru or Ni), that is to say, on their capability to shift the conversion of CO into CH₄ after carbon CO₂ is partially reduced to CO.

In Figure 66 is shown (extracted from [55]) the block scheme of the proposed Sabatier process.

In general, catalytic methanation reactors are operated at temperatures between 200 and 550 °C and at pressures between 1 to 100 bar. The simplest and most economical reactor arrangement is composed of a certain number of adiabatic beds with intercooling [55].

Since the methane emerging from the carbon dioxide scrubbing still contains water vapor, it is dehydrated via the Pressure Swing Adsorption (PSA) technique and the moisture recycled to the upstream CO₂ wash [55].

Figure 66: Block scheme of the Sabatier process with recycled reactor

8.2.2 Separation

In cases where the blends of hydrogen with methane is to be burnt for fuel value, the mixture may be used directly (although some modifications of burners may be needed for high hydrogen content). In cases where hydrogen alone is required, the hydrogen in the natural gas pipeline must be extracted

Erreur ! Source du renvoi introuvable.

Deliverable 3.3, Revision A

from the enriched natural gas mixture. Using an efficient separation process, hydrogen can be extracted at desired locations along the grid for different application.

There are only a few studies available in the literature which address the separation of H₂ from natural gas.

PSA is a common technology for the separation of gases at a high pressure and has been widely used in industry for decades to purify hydrogen from reforming gases. It has several advantages over other technologies including cryogenic distillation, absorption, membrane, and electrochemical membranes. Specifically, PSA has the ability to operate with low energy consumption, requires low cost, and is capable of producing high purity product at high recovery. However, there are only a few studies reported to date on PSA technology for the separation of H₂ from natural gas in the literature, and there is therefore a need to study the technology performance of a custom designed PSA system to extract H₂ from natural gas [56].

ECCN: N

AL: N

8.3 Annex 3 – Hydrogen Backbone – details on corridors

The next sections provide in-depth information, extracted from the “Implementation roadmap – cross border projects and cost update” delivered by EHB [57] about projects planned for commissioning by EHB partners in the coming years. The projects are arranged and color-coded by corridor.

Since Germany is part of all EHB corridors its transmission network is included separately because that would otherwise have been discussed in multiple corridors.

8.3.1 Corridor A – North Africa and Southern Europe

The North Africa and Southern Europe corridor (shown yellow in Figure 67) aims to deliver hydrogen from North Africa and Southern Italy towards Central Europe.

Hydrogen from North Africa will first be injected to the Italian Hydrogen Backbone (SouthH2 & Sunshyne corridors), consisting of approximately 2300 km of pipeline (of which 75 % is repurposed). After serving domestic demand in Italy, hydrogen will be moved into additional central European countries. Within Austria (in addition to serving domestic demand) hydrogen will be transported towards Germany and connected to storage facilities along the route.

Corridor A is connected with the East and Southeastern Europe Corridor (Corridor E), via Slovakia and Czech Republic. Additionally, a connection to the Slovenian Hydrogen Backbone will not only supply national demand but also enable further connection to Croatia.

ECCN: N
AL: N

Figure 67: North Africa and Southern Europe corridor.

8.3.2 Corridor B – Southwest Europe and North Africa

The Southwest Europe & North Africa corridor (shown green in Figure 68) is intended to transport hydrogen from the Southwest Europe to demand centers in Germany and beyond.

Corridor B connects hydrogen networks in Portugal, Spain, France and Germany. The Spanish Hydrogen Backbone collects multiple supply sources from around Spain and allows connection to North African project developments, making it one of the most promising hydrogen production locations in Europe. The connection between Spain and France is made by traversing the Mediterranean Sea as an offshore pipeline from Barcelona to Marseille. From Marseille onwards, the hydrogen network branches into two directions, through France (via HySoW) towards the Atlantic coast and as connection to Western European countries (via HyFen).

Figure 68: North Africa and Southern Europe corridor.

8.3.3 Corridor C – North Sea

The North Sea corridor (shown purple in Figure 69) is intended to transport hydrogen from the Norwegian Coast and from Denmark to demand centers in the western part of Germany.

The energy feedstock for hydrogen production in this corridor is provided by the offshore wind potential in the region.

In addition, the supply of hydrogen in this corridor through the import of hydrogen derivatives is also planned via ports such as Rotterdam and Antwerp.

Figure 69: North Sea corridor.

8.3.4 Corridor D – Nordic and Baltic Regions

The Nordic and Baltic corridor (shown blue in Figure 70) aims to transport hydrogen from Nordic and Baltic Regions to Western and Central Europe.

The Nordic and Baltic regions have significant renewable energy resources based on low-cost renewable energy. Three major projects are planned to connect these regions with demand regions:

- Nordic Hydrogen Route-Bothnian Bay project, which connects the northern parts of Finland and Sweden to demand centers in these regions.
- Nordic-Baltic Hydrogen corridor project, which connects the future Baltic hydrogen market with Germany. The Nordic-Baltic Hydrogen Corridor is also connected to the Nordic Hydrogen Route-Bothnian Bay corridor.
- Baltic Sea Hydrogen Collector offshore project, which connects Finland, Sweden, and Germany, as well as the energy islands in the region.

AL: N
ECCN: N

Figure 70: Nordic and Baltic regions corridor.

8.3.5 Corridor E – East and Southeastern Europe

The East and Southeastern Europe corridor (shown red in Figure 71) is intended to transport hydrogen from Greece or from Ukraine through Bulgaria, Romania, Hungary, Slovakia, and Austria to Central Europe.

This corridor connects with North Africa and Southern Europe corridor (corridor A). To allow flows in both directions, technical flexibility of the transmission system is required, especially in Slovakia and Austria.

Figure 71: East and Southeastern Europe corridor.

8.3.6 Transmission Network in Germany

Germany, that is part of all EHB corridors, is expected to import large amounts of hydrogen to meet the largest national hydrogen demand.

The transmission network in Germany⁶ (shown in Figure 72) will make it possible to connect domestic hydrogen production and hydrogen imports with German demand centers.

⁶ The final transmission network, with a expected total length about 11200 km, is still under discussion

Figure 72 Hydrogen transmission network in Germany

ECCN: N
AL: N

8.4 Annex 4 – Emerging hydrogen applications: Transport

8.4.1 Hydrogen

Hydrogen is the simplest form of all molecules; it has the lowest energy content by volume, but it has the highest energy content of any fuel by weight. Hydrogen has the capability to produce electricity in a fuel cell (up to 39,39 kWh/kg, which surpasses the energy density of most batteries).

There are various types of fuel cell systems. However, the principle of their function is similar. For a fuel cell system, three pillars are required: an anode, a cathode, and an electrolyte⁷ (located between the cathode and the anode). A fuel cell system is composed of several individual cells, but each have the same fundamental components.

Figure 73: Fuel cell operation diagram

From a user's point of view, the most notable differences between FCEVs and BEVs are the driving range and the refueling style. FCEVs have above a 500 km driving range and can be refueled in less than 10 minutes at a hydrogen refueling station, which is more comparable to a traditional ICE vehicle.

Hydrogen storage is the one of the most important research issues in the development of FCEVs. Hydrogen storage systems are under development to introduce new methods to meet the needs of customers. Due to hydrogen's low energy-density, it is difficult to store enough on-board a vehicle to obtain adequate driving-range without the storage container being too large or too heavy. In the Figure 74, extracted from [58] is presented the arrangement of components in a FCEV.

⁷ Fuel cell are categorized by the type of electrolyte.

AL: N
ECCN: N

Figure 74: Arrangement of components in a FCEV

8.4.2 Ammonia

In recent decades, ammonia has been proposed as a transport fuel for buses, trains and aircraft. While numerous R&D projects are focused on those areas, ammonia is proposed for more widespread use as a marine fuel for international shipping, to replace heavy fuel oil and LNG.

Around 95 % of all freight transport takes place at sea, consuming around 10 % of the total transport energy worldwide and accounting for 2,6 % of global greenhouse gas emissions.

Maritime engine manufacturers expect to commercialize ammonia-fueled engines by 2024 or 2025, for both new builds and retrofits. Dual fuel engines allow for fuel flexibility during the implementation of ammonia as a fuel. [5]

8.4.3 Methanol

Methanol's use in transportation fuels is growing. Methanol is a versatile, affordable alternative transportation fuel due to its efficient combustion, ease of distribution, and wide availability around the globe. Methanol is used in gasoline blends around the world at low (3 – 5 %), mid (15 – 30 %), and high (50 – 100 %) volume percentages, and as a diesel substitute for use in heavy-duty vehicles. [15]

While methanol can be used in Internal Combustion Engine (ICE) vehicles, it can also be a fuel for hybrid vehicle (ICE/electric) and FCEV⁸.

Therefore, an added benefit of using methanol is that the same fuel can power both ICE vehicles and FCEVs, leading to a seamless transition to these more advanced powertrains.

The use of liquid methanol avoids the need for costly on-board systems able to store and transfer hydrogen gas safely under extreme pressure (350-700 bar) in FCEVs. [59]

Methanol is proposed for use as a marine fuel for international shipping, to replace heavy fuel oil and LNG. According to [60], the year 2023 could fairly be called the year that methanol went mainstream, with new methanol-capable vessel orders ahead of those for other dual fuel ship types.

N
ECCN:
AL: N

⁸ Methanol is reformed on board the vehicle to hydrogen, which is fed to a fuel cell to charge batteries in a BEV or provide direct propulsion in a FCEV

8.5 Annex 5 – Co-electrolysis of carbon dioxide and water.

Syngas, a gas mixture mainly composed of carbon monoxide (CO) hydrogen (H₂), can be used to produce chemicals, pharmaceuticals, fertilizers, solvents, plastics, and chemical intermediates. In the practical production process, a specific ratio of syngas is required for different downstream applications, for example, a H₂:CO ratio of 2:1 is suitable for methanol synthesis, whereas the efficient Fischer-Tropsch process requires a H₂:CO ratio of 0,3–4. [61]

Syngas is produced by many pathways such as SRM, ATR of methane, POX of methane, coal gasification, biomass PYR, etc... These synthetic processes not only use non-renewable fossil energy as feedstock but also consume a high amount of energy to surmount the energy barrier of the reaction, resulting in high fossil energy consumption and a lot of CO₂ emissions.

In CO₂/H₂O co-electrolysis, CO₂ is converted to CO, through the Electrochemical Reduction of CO₂ (CO₂RR), and H₂O to H₂. Therefore, the CO₂RR, that can be driven by electricity generated from renewable energy sources, is an attractive way of upgrading CO₂ to value-added chemicals.

8.5.1 Electrochemical reduction of carbon dioxide

Thermodynamically, CO₂RR can produce a wide range of products. The reactions take the general form as follows [62]:

Where n is from 2 to 18, depending on the exact reaction pathways.

The large variety of reactions and C-products that can be derived from the CO₂RR is shown in Figure 75, extracted from [62]. This figure also shows for each reaction the equilibrium potential E⁰, vs Reversible Hydrogen Electrode (RHE)⁹, at ambient conditions.

Reaction	E ⁰ (V vs. RHE)
CO ₂ + 2H ⁺ + 2e ⁻ → CO + H ₂ O	-0.10
CO ₂ + 2H ⁺ + 2e ⁻ → HCOOH	-0.12
CO ₂ + 6H ⁺ + 6e ⁻ → CH ₃ OH + H ₂ O	0.03
2CO ₂ + 8H ⁺ + 8e ⁻ → CH ₃ COOH + 3H ₂ O	0.11
2CO ₂ + 10H ⁺ + 10e ⁻ → CH ₃ CHO + 3H ₂ O	0.06
2CO ₂ + 12H ⁺ + 12e ⁻ → C ₂ H ₅ OH + 3H ₂ O	0.09
2CO ₂ + 12H ⁺ + 12e ⁻ → C ₂ H ₄ + 4H ₂ O	0.08
2CO ₂ + 14H ⁺ + 14e ⁻ → C ₂ H ₆ + 4H ₂ O	0.14
2CO ₂ + 16H ⁺ + 16e ⁻ → C ₂ H ₅ CHO + 5H ₂ O	0.09
3CO ₂ + 18H ⁺ + 18e ⁻ → C ₃ H ₇ OH + 5H ₂ O	0.10

Figure 75: Electrochemical reduction of CO₂ pathways.

Recent techno-economic analyses have concluded that the electrochemical production of CO has the greatest chance to become cost competitive with regard to current chemical routes.

⁹ RHE is a reference electrode, more specifically a subtype of the standard hydrogen electrodes, for electrochemical processes. Unlike the standard hydrogen electrode, its measured potential does change with the pH, so it can be directly used in the electrolyte.

In a Membrane Electrode Assembly (MEA) based coelectrolysis cell, constituted by a cathode and an anode fed with CO₂ and H₂O, the corresponding reduction and oxidation reactions lead to the production of CO and O₂, respectively (see Figure 76, extracted from [63]).

Figure 76: Co-electrolysis of CO₂ and H₂O

The pH at which the reactions take place has an important effect on the selectivity of the different reactions. In the Pourbaix diagram, extracted from [63] is displayed the effect of the electrolyte's pH on the reversible potential (E_{rev}) of the cathodic and anodic electrochemical reactions.

Figure 77: Carbon dioxide electrolysis Pourboix diagram.

As can be seen in Figure 78 (reactions 1 and 2), the E_{rev} vs. pH line for CO₂ reduction to CO almost overlaps with the cathode side reaction of Hydrogen Evolution Reaction (HER) and, as a result, hydrogen is a common co-electrolyzer cathode by-product.

Co-electrolyzer cathodes are operated at alkaline to quasi-neutral pHs at which the fed CO₂ readily equilibrates with OH⁻ to yield bicarbonate anions. (reactions 6 and 7)

Some MEA configurations are Anion Exchange Membrane (AEM), Reverse Bias Bipolar Membrane (RB-BPM) and Forward Bias Bipolar Membrane (FB-BPM).

AEM: in this configuration bicarbonate anions are transported from cathode to anode, across the membrane (crossover), where they get oxidized back to CO₂. This transportation leads to a low overall CO₂ utilization of the device in which only less than half of all the fed carbon dioxide is actually devoted to the production of the desired C products.

Figure 78: AEM co-electrolysis configuration.

RB-BPM: in this configuration the crossover problem of AEM is overcome by substituting the AEM with a Bipolar Membrane (BPM), in which an Anion Exchange Layer (AEL) and a Cation Exchange Layer (CEL) are laminated against each other in which water is split into protons and hydroxyl groups at the interface between CEL and AEL. This configuration has mostly been implemented with the BPM operated in a so-called RB mode, in which the AEL and CEL are located at the cell's anode and cathode, respectively.

Figure 79: RB-BPM co-electrolysis configuration.

FB-BPM: in this configuration bicarbonate anions (produced at the anode and transported across the membrane AEL) and react with the protons from the acidic CEL yielding CO₂ and H₂O. Using the FB-BPM configuration the crossover problem is completely suppressed.

Figure 80: FB-BPM co-electrolysis configuration.

8.5.2 Electrocatalytic reduction of carbon dioxide and water

When CO₂ reduction is carried out in aqueous solution, due to the similar electrochemical reduction potentials of -0,10 and 0 V versus RHE, HER will inevitably occur. Therefore the main products of the electrochemical reduction of CO₂ and H₂O are CO and H₂ (syngas).

Cathode:

Anode:

And the overall reaction is:

In addition the WGSR can be used to adjust the H₂/CO ratio to optimize the downstream chemical process.

An endothermic reaction under high-temperature conditions, such as CO₂ and/or H₂O electrolysis, is thermodynamically advantageous because most of the energy required for the reaction can be provided in the form of heat. The high-temperature operation of the Solid Oxide Electrolysis Cells (SOEC) reduces the demand for electricity and shows great potential for further development.

Although the electrochemical reduction of CO₂ in aqueous solution to produce tunable syngas has unique advantages from the aspects of energy and environment, there are still urgent challenges that need to be resolved. The main challenge is to develop an efficient electrocatalyst to overcome the reaction energy barriers¹⁰ and accelerate reaction rates. [61]

In Figure 81, extracted from [64], is displayed graphically the electrocatalytic reduction of carbon dioxide and water using SOEC.

N
ECCN:
N
AL:

Figure 81: Electrocatalytic reduction of carbon dioxide and water in a SOEC

¹⁰ Due to the stable linear structure of the CO₂ molecule, it is necessary to provide high-energy electrons and protons to break the C = O bond